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Working Paper

A METHODOLOGICAL INQUIRY INTO THE DATA GENERATING PROCESS CONCERNING NEW JOBS AND SKILLS

Taxonomy

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Abstract

This paper presents the findings of six case studies, each of which makes use of web data, to carry out research on occupations and skills. The idea behind the case studies is to put into test a series of methodologies and assess what one can learn. Four case studies are based on job advertisements, one case study is based on meta data, and one case study is based on a combination of both data sources. By analysing these data, we are able to better understand what types of occupations and skills are high in demand, how these differ across countries and sectors and related topics. More specifically, our case studies cover mismatches between the educational requirements in vacancies and educational attainments of job holders in the Czech Republic, the requirements listed in job vacancies for the 30 most-frequently-advertised occupations in the US in general and IT skills in particular, foreign language skills requirements in the Visegrad region and the demand for non-cognitive skills. One of the case studies is devoted to a pilot of a new method to detect new and emerging occupations. This paper summarises the main findings of each of these case studies. It shows that web data are a highly valuable data source for labour market research and research concerning occupations and skills in particular.

This report constitutes Milestone MS97 'Benchmark data generating processes concerning new skills and jobs', for Work Package 21 of the InGRID project.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, web data have increasingly been used for labour market research. We contribute to this rapidly advancing field by focusing on how such data can be used to do research on new occupations and skills. In order to assess the potential of web data in this area, we carried out *six case studies*. These case studies cover a range of topics, from the mismatch between the educational requirements listed in job advertisements and the educational attainment of job holders, over foreign language skills or IT skills requirements, to a new method to capture new and emerging occupations.

In this paper, we present our *taxonomy report*, which outlines the findings of these six case studies. Four of these case studies are based on a sample of *vacancies*, collected from online job portals. For one case study, we only used the *meta data* available on such job boards (e.g. the occupational classification and its corresponding tags). In the remaining case study, we combine both methods (e.g. new and emerging occupations are identified on the basis of meta data, subsequently more information on them is gathered from job advertisements). For the case studies that rely on data extracted from vacancies, we use web crawling to collect the data. As a second step, we perform a semantic analysis to derive information from the vacancy text (e.g. tasks and responsibilities). This procedure is explained in a number of recent papers by Capiluppi & Baravalle (2010), Kuhn & Shen (2013) and Carnevale *et al.* (2014), who also discuss the advantages and limitations of this approach. While data collection is relatively easy and fast, data processing - such as the semantic analysis - is less straightforward. Given the high level of detail that job listings offer, they are an interesting data source to study occupations and skills. Meta data, on the other hand, are easier to obtain and analyse than vacancies, but contain less information. Those data do, nevertheless, allow us to study occupations and skills, as we demonstrate in our work.

This paper is the counterpart of the methodological report that we present along with this report as a deliverable for *Work Package 21* of the *InGRID FP7 project (Task 21.1.2, MS97)*. While the methodological report introduces the methodology and data that we used in our work, the current paper is a *taxonomy report*. Its aim is to present the results of six case studies that we carried out to assess the potential role of web data for labour market research (with a focus on occupations and skills in particular). In the taxonomy report, we explain what our research question was for each of these case studies, why it is interesting and what we have learned from our analyses. The methodology and data used to obtain these findings are only briefly recalled. We refer readers who would like to know more about these steps to the methodology report.

Given that both the methodology and the taxonomy are deliverables of the same work package and closely related to each other, we illustrate in Figure 1.1 below precisely how these reports are linked. In Figure 1.1 we compare the traditional research approach with our approach. Traditionally, a research paper describes all phases of a research project: the framework in which the researcher operates, previous literature on the topic, the data and methodology used, and the results and conclusions. In our work, we also cover these different dimensions but we have separated them into three distinct papers. Each of these papers serves as a deliverable for Work Package 21 of the project. More specifically, we prepared a *state of the art report* (which reviews the academic and policy literature) (Beblavý *et al.*, 2016a), a *methodology report* (which discusses methodology and data) and a *taxonomy report* (which is dedicated to the results and conclusions). In this way, we can carefully assess each of the different dimensions. In addition, this allows us to easily compare the results and methodologies of

the different case studies. As all papers are closely linked to each other, we advise readers to consider them together and to also take a look at the other two reports when going through one of them.

Figure 1.1 Typical research set-up and how our approach differs

In the remainder of this taxonomy report, we present the six case studies. Each time, we briefly recall the scope of the case study as well as the methodology and data used, and then discuss the main findings obtained. Table 1.1 below summarises the case studies. It describes their scope, data and main results. For a subset of the case studies, further details are presented in Tijdens *et al.* (2015), Beblavý *et al.* (2016b), Beblavý *et al.* (2016c) and Beblavý *et al.* (2016d). Section 3 concludes the report.

Table 1.1 Overview of the six case studies

Case	DATA			RESEARCH			
	Type	Timing	Source	Country	Occupations	Focus	Main results
1	Vacancies	December 2013	EURES for the vacancies	CZ	279 occupations, all skill levels	Mismatches between labour demand and supply	Substantial mismatch for most occupations, link between demand and educational requirements
2	Vacancies	September 2013-August 2014	Burning Glass Technologies	US	30-most-frequently advertised occupations, all skill levels	All requirements (education, experience, cognitive skills, non-cognitive skills and other requirements)	US employers are fairly demanding even for low-skilled occupations, especially education, experience and service skills matter, also high demand for other soft skills
3	Vacancies	September 2013-August 2014	Burning Glass Technologies	US	30-most-frequently advertised occupations, all skill levels	IT skills, sub-divided into basic/general skills, intermediate skills, advanced skills	Basic IT skills are rather widespread, intermediate level especially in office jobs, clear pattern in terms of demand across the skill levels of occupations
4	Meta data from job boards (also vacancies in second stage)	July 2015 – December 2015	11 online job boards	BE, CZ, DE, DK, ES, FR, HU, IT, PL, SK, UK	All occupations are considered, new occupation tags are captured	All requirements, not only in a single country but also cross-country	Occupation tags are an easy and fast way to identify potentially new or emerging occupations, though a lot of variation depending on the portal and country
5	Meta data from job boards	17 July 2015	4 online job boards	Visegrad: CZ, HU, PL, SK	All occupations in a first stage, in second stage 59 occupations were retained	Foreign language skills (English, German and Russian in particular)	English language skills are widely demanded and come with a wage premium, no such a relation for German
6	Vacancies	Several time frames	Several data sources	CZ, DK, IE, SK, US	Wide range of occupations, of different skills levels	Non-cognitive or soft skills	Non-cognitive skills prevalent in occupations of every skill level, difference across the countries are notable

2. Case Study 1: ‘Do educational requirements in vacancies match the educational attainments of job-holders? An analysis of web-based data for 279 occupations in the Czech Republic’

(Tijdens et al., 2015)

As a first case study, we focused on the Czech Republic and examined whether there is a mismatch between the educational requirements that employers demand and the educational attainment that job-holders have. Data on the educational requirements of employers were derived from a sample of job advertisements published on EURES (4-digit ISCO). Data on the educational attainment of job holders are extracted from WageIndicator (also 4-digit ISCO). As the results of this case study are presented in detail in another deliverable of the InGRID project (see Tijdens et al., 2015), we here recall only the key findings of the paper.

2.1 Results on supply and demand by occupation (ratios)

A comparison of labour demand and supply for 279 occupations reveals that there is a mismatch between labour demand and supply for the vast majority of these occupations. In 32% of the cases, demand is at least five times the supply, whereas the opposite holds in 25% of the cases. Only for very few occupations, demand and supply are balanced. In other words, there is a substantial variation in demand and supply across occupations.

We further find that the relationship between the demand for an occupation and the educational requirements in the job advertisements is negative: as the amount of unfilled vacancies rises, the educational requirements become less important. A similar negative relation is detected between the demand for an occupation and job holders’ educational attainments, though only for medium and high education levels.

2.2 Results on educational requirements and attainments by occupation

As the mean level of education requested in the job advertisements across the different occupations does not correspond to the mean level of educational attainments of the job holders working in the occupation, a further analysis was carried out. In general, the educational attainments of job holders appeared to exceed the requirements listed in the vacancies. This finding is confirmed regardless of whether the lowest, mean or highest education levels are used. The range of educational requirements is wide in medium- and high-skilled occupations and limited in low-skilled occupations, while the opposite applies when educational attainments are considered (broad range in low-skilled, but condensed in medium- and high-skilled).

2.3 Summary

- There is a mismatch in the number of vacancies available and the number of job holders on the labour market: in most occupations there is a substantial difference between these two (and for a considerable share of occupations, the difference could be regarded as excessive).
- In terms of educational attainments and requirements, it becomes clear that the attainments of the job holders surpass the requirements in the vacancies.
- There is a negative correlation between demand for an occupation and the educational requirements.

3. Case Study 2: ‘Skills requirements for the 30 most-frequently advertised occupations in the US: an analysis based on online vacancy data’

(Beblaryj *et al.*, 2016c)

In the second case study, we focused our attention on labour demand and again used a sample of job advertisements that were published online to get some more insight into the requirements that employers have. Our analysis was based on a sample of about two million vacancies for the 30 most-frequently-advertised occupations in the United States. This sample was obtained from Burning Glass Technologies, a US-based company that provides job market analytics and vacancy data. The job advertisements on which our analysis is based were collected over the 12-month period between September 2013 and August 2014. As explained in more depth in our methodological report, Burning Glass data are highly structured, coded, categorised, and ready-for-use.

The list of the 30 most-frequently-advertised occupations is represented in Appendix 1. It covers *low-skilled, medium-skilled and high-skilled occupations*, including cooks, office clerks, truck drivers, managers and nurses. To determine the skill level of an occupation, we follow Kureková *et al.* (2015) and consider occupations with ISCO code 9 as low-skilled, occupations with ISCO codes 4-8 as medium-skilled and occupations with ISCO codes 1-3 as high-skilled. Out of the 30 occupations in our sample, two are low-skilled, 20 are medium-skilled and eight are high-skilled according to this definition. In our sample, we find occupations of all ISCO classes, with the exception of ISCO class 6. This implies that our sample covers occupations of different complexities and with different education and skills requirements. While some of these occupations are specific to certain sectors, others can be found throughout the economy.

For these 30 occupations, we analysed the requirements that US employers specify in their job advertisements. We started our work by identifying six types of qualifications, *education and formal qualifications, cognitive skills, non-cognitive skills, experience, appearance and other requirements*, which we aim to capture in the vacancies using a set of keywords - or combinations thereof (listed in Table 3.1). Each of these types can be subdivided into sub-types, such as ‘formal education’ and ‘specialised training and licenses’ for the first type, ‘generic cognitive skills’ and ‘specific cognitive skills’ for the second type or ‘social non-cognitive skills’ and ‘personal non-cognitive skills’ for the third type. In each case, we compare our list of keywords with the vacancy text and keep track of the number and share of job advertisements - in total and by occupation - that contain one or more of these keywords.

Our focus on these six categories is motivated by earlier work such as Kureková *et al.* (2015). In addition, by taking a broad perspective, we aspire to better understand what requirements are particularly important to employers and how this differs across the 30 occupations. We devote special attention to the *role of cognitive and non-cognitive skills*, as there is an ongoing debate on whether cognitive or non-cognitive skills are the most relevant on the labour market (see e.g. Maxwell, 2006; Kureková *et al.*, 2015). In our case study, cognitive skills are defined as ‘skills that are typically identified with intelligence and the ability to solve abstract problems (Kureková *et al.*, 2015, p. 8)’. Cognitive skills can be ‘generic’ (e.g. problem-solving) or ‘specific’ (e.g. ICT skills). Non-cognitive skills are defined

as ‘personality traits that are to some extent correlated with intelligence measures’ (Brunello & Schotter, 2011). These skills can be ‘social’ or ‘personal’ in nature. Results for the non-cognitive skills are presented in case study 6.

Table 3.1 Overview of the keywords used to identify six types of qualifications

Qualification	Sub-type		Keywords used for identification
Education & formal qualifications		Formal education	Diploma, GED, bachelor, college, university, degree, high school
		Specialised training & licenses	Apprenticeship, training, card, certificate, certification, certified, CDA, ASE, CPR, AED
Cognitive skills	Specific	Computer skills	Computer, PC, CRM, Microsoft (Office, Word, Excel, Power Point, Outlook, and Access), Windows, SAP
		Analytical skills	Mathematics, analytical, logic, quantitative
		Language skills	Bilingual, English, Spanish, language
		Driver’s license	Driver’s license
	Generic	Ability to learn	Ability to learn, able to learn
Non-cognitive skills	Social	Communication skills	Communication, speak, write, articulate, verbal, interact, communicate
		Service skills	Client, customer, guest, needs, attention
		Team-work skills	Team, attitude, focus, leader work, spirit, environment
	Personal	Creativity	Creative
		Flexibility	Flexible, stay overnight, travel, shifts, work evenings
		Independence	Self-motivated, initiative, independent
		Pleasant demeanour & manners	Attitude, positive, mature, helpful, confident, enthusiastic, professional
		Reliability	Attention to detail, dependable, reliable
		Stress-resistant	Calm, stress, crisis situation
		Timeliness & punctuality	Timely manner, deadlines, act quickly, punctual, prioritise
Experience	Experience	Experience combined with year, month, work, preferred, desirable	
Appearance/look	Appearance	Well-groomed, clean, neat, professional	
Other	Citizenship	US citizen, citizenship	
	Criminal record	No criminal record, clean criminal record	
	Drug testing	Drugs, drug testing	

3.1 The sum of skills and the sum of all requirements

As a first step in the analysis, we calculated two measures that allow us to capture how much structure employers put into their vacancies and what qualifications are listed the most (in general and across occupations) (Kureková *et al.*, 2012; Kureková *et al.*, 2015). The first measure that we use is the ‘*sum of skills*’. This measure captures requirements for education, cognitive skills and non-cognitive skills from the vacancies. It is equal to the sum of the percentage of vacancies that refer to education and formal qualifications, cognitive skills and non-cognitive skills. For this measure, we take 17 qualifications and skills into account, which are listed in Table 3.1. In addition to the sum of skills, we use a second measure to capture the ‘*sum of all requirements*’. This measure is calculated as the sum of the

percentage of vacancies that refer to education and formal qualifications, cognitive skills, non-cognitive skills, experience, appearance and other factors. In other words, it captures each of the six types of requirements that are presented in Table 3.1 (17 skills and five additional aspects, based on the 'sum of skills' measure). For both measures, it is not their precise value that matters. Instead, the idea is that these measures can be used to rank occupations so as to better understand for which occupations vacancies are rich in terms of the requirements mentioned and how this changes with their complexity. In other words, the sum of skills and the sum of all requirements cannot be interpreted in absolute terms; it is the relative interpretation of the measures that counts.

An example of how the sum of skills and the sum of all requirements are calculated is presented in Table 3.2 for the 'general and operations managers'. The sum of skills is equal to the sum of the percentage of vacancies listing requirements related to education and formal qualifications (75%+13%), cognitive skills (32%+14%+17% for the specific cognitive skills; +2%+6% for the generic cognitive skills) and non-cognitive skills (27%+48%+48% for the social non-cognitive skills; +40%+25%+1%+7%+38%+33%+5% for the personal non-cognitive skills). The sum of all these percentages is 431%. The sum of all requirements is based on the sum of skills, but also includes other information. More specifically, for the general and operations managers, it is equal to 431% (sum of skills) +1% (percentage of vacancies with requirements in terms of appearance) +40% (experience) +16% (other factors: criminal record 7%, drug testing 7%, citizenship 2%). This results in a total of 488%.

Table 3.2 Example of the calculation of the sum of skills and the sum of all requirements for the occupation 'general and operations managers' (based on 30,641 vacancies)

Education & formal qualifications	Cognitive Skills	Non-Cognitive Skills	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Education: 75% - Specialised training & licenses: 13% <p>Sum = 88%</p>	<p>Specific Cognitive Skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Computer skills: 32% - Analytical skills: 14% - Language skills: 17% <p>Generic Cognitive Skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Driving license: 2% - Ability to learn: 6% <p>Sum = 71%</p>	<p>Social Non-Cognitive Skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication skills: 27% - Service skills: 48% - Team-working skills: 48% <p>Personal Non-Cognitive Skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Timeliness: 40% - Independence: 25% - Reliability: 1% - Demeanour: 7% - Creativity: 38% - Flexibility: 33% - Stress-resistant: 5% <p>Sum = 272%</p>	<p><i>Sum of skills = 431%</i> = 88% + 71% + 272%</p>
Appearance	Experience	Other	
<p>Pleasant physical appearance: 1%</p> <p>Sum = 1%</p>	<p>Experience: 40%</p> <p>Sum = 40%</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Criminal record: 7% - Drug testing: 7% - Citizenship: 2% <p>Sum = 16%</p>	<p><i>Sum of all = 488%</i> = 431% + 1% + 40% + 16%</p>

Table 3.3 presents the sum of skills and the sum of all requirements for each of the 30 most-frequently-advertised occupations. The *sum of skills* across all occupations is equal to 377% (when all vacancies are considered at once). For individual occupations, this number ranges from 225% to 525%. Hence, there clearly is a lot of variation across the 30 occupations. For four occupations the sum of skills does not reach 300%: ‘janitors and cleaners’, ‘labourers’, ‘personal care aides’ and ‘maintenance workers’. For 16 occupations, the sum of skills falls between 300% and 400%. The five highest-ranking occupations are security guards (525%), tellers (477%), meeting, convention and event planners (453%), general and operations managers (431%) and first-line office supervisors (430%).

The *sum of all requirements* is also reported in Table 3.3. It is strongly and positively correlated with the sum of skills. The sum of all requirements is equal to 445% when all vacancies are considered at once. This value varies between 289% and 650% across the 30 occupations.

From Table 3.3, it is clear that employers are relatively demanding in the vacancies that they post, even for low-skilled jobs. This result has also been documented in other work, such as Maxwell (2006), Kureková *et al.* (2012) and Kureková *et al.* (2015). Another key conclusion is that there is substantial variation in the requirements demanded across the 30 occupations. This variation is related to the complexity of the occupations (captured by the ISCO codes), at least to some extent.

Table 3.3 Sum of skills and sum of all requirements in total and by occupation

ISCO	Occupation	Sum of skills (%)	Sum of all requirements (%)
1	General and Operations Managers	431	488
2	Computer Support Specialists	405	467
2	HR Specialists	375	460
3	Bookkeeping, Accounting, Auditing Clerks	358	425
3	First-Line Office Supervisors	430	500
3	Medical Assistants	340	418
3	Meeting, Convention, Event Planners	453	607
3	Nursing Assistant	321	382
4	Cashiers	357	410
4	CS Representatives	420	484
4	Medical Secretaries	341	399
4	Office Clerks	333	399
4	Secretaries	373	442
4	Tellers	477	542
5	Combined Food Preparation Workers	318	384
5	Cooks, Restaurant	300	370
5	Merchandise Displayers	422	501
5	Personal Care Aides	269	326
5	Retail Salesperson	386	430
5	Sale Worker Supervisors	419	466
5	Sales Agents, Financial Services	415	479
5	Sales Representative Wholesale	380	447
5	Security Guards	525	650
5	Supervisors of Food Preparation, Serving Workers	364	415
7	Installation, Maintenance, Repair Workers	376	472
7	Maintenance Worker	298	379
8	Heavy Truck And Tractor Drivers	316	400
8	Light Truck, Delivery Service Drivers	349	440
9	Janitors And Cleaners	225	289
9	Labourers	255	331
	Across occupations (all vacancies considered at once)	377	445

The link between the sum of skills/the sum of all requirements and the complexity of a group of occupations is further explored in Table 3.4, which presents the averages of the measures by ISCO category. These results, in combination with those presented above, show that the employers are rather demanding: for the 17 skill demands, the average is 360%. When the other factors are introduced as well, the average is 440%. This conclusion also applies to low-skilled and medium-skilled jobs (even though scores are decreasing, the averages remain relatively high and are stable in the middle of the distribution). The correlation between the ISCO coding and the sum of skills is -0.51

(as occupations become more complex, requirements tend to increase, as one would expect). The correlation between the ISCO classification and the sum of all requirements is -0.42.

Table 3.4 Average sum of skills and sum of all requirements by ISCO class (in %)

ISCO	Average sum of skills	Average sum of all requirements
1	431	488
2	390	464
3	380	466
4	384	446
5	380	447
7	337	426
8	333	420
9	240	310

3.2 Specific results on education, training and experience

When we focus on the extent to which vacancies refer to education and experience in Table 3.5, we notice that these requirements are made explicit in the majority of the advertisements. More specifically, 67% of the job vacancies examined request formal education gained through full time study (i.e. having at least a high school degree in our study). Across the 30 occupations, this percentage ranges from 45 to 83% (see Table 3.5). On average, 52 (ISCO group 8) to 75% (ISCO group 1) of vacancies refer to formal education. These results suggest that education is an important filter for most employers. In fact, for 28 out of the 30 occupations - including labourers - more than half of the vacancies demands at least some level or form of formal education. For 19 occupations, at least two-thirds of the advertisements comprise formal education requirements.

In contrast, only 16% of all job advertisements requires specialised training or licenses. In this case, there is a lot more variation across occupations, as shown in Table 3.5. For 10 occupations, the percentage of vacancies that refer to specialised training or licenses is below 10%, whereas for three occupations it is higher than 30%. These three occupations are meeting, convention, event planners (37%), medical assistants (64%) and nursing assistants (77%). Across ISCO groups, the average percentages of job advertisements that refers to specialised training or licenses are 13% (ISCO 1), 15% (ISCO 2), 40% (ISCO 3), 12% (ISCO 4), 14% (ISCO 5), 20% (ISCO 7), 10% (ISCO 8) and 22% (ISCO 9). This suggests that specialised training/licenses are relevant for certain occupations in particular. More specifically, of the six occupations for which the number is 25% or higher, four are health-related professions.

Like formal education, experience is one of the most common requirements: it appears in about 38% of the job advertisements. The share of vacancies that refer to experience ranges from 21 to 51% across the 30 occupations. With the exception of 13 occupations, at least 40% of the job advertisements include experience. The largest shares of vacancies that demand experience are found for HR specialists (51%), computer support specialists (49%), medical assistants, bookkeeping, accounting, auditing clerks, secretaries and medical secretaries (47% in each case). There is a small negative correlation of -0.24 between the ISCO classification and the percentage of vacancies that request experience. As occupations become more and more complex, they thus tend to require experience more frequently. Although one can expect that the experience required for a job depends on the position to be filled in within a company, it is clear that experience is an important filter in the selection and recruitment process. Moreover, for many occupations it is a qualification that workers need in order to be able to perform the work.

Table 3.5 Share of vacancies referring to education, training and experience

ISCO	Occupation	Share with education requirements (%)	Share with specialised training/licenses (%)	Share with experience (%)
1	General and Operations Managers	75	13	40
2	Computer Support Specialists	73	16	49
2	HR Specialists	69	14	51
3	Bookkeeping, Accounting, Auditing Clerks	65	9	47
3	First-Line Office Supervisors	72	14	44
3	Medical Assistants	59	64	47
3	Meeting, Convention, Event Planners	60	37	31
3	Nursing Assistant	64	77	36
4	Cashiers	81	5	32
4	CS Representatives	66	8	40
4	Medical Secretaries	56	25	47
4	Office Clerks	66	16	43
4	Secretaries	70	13	47
4	Tellers	83	4	43
5	Combined Food Preparation Workers	63	13	33
5	Cooks, Restaurant	67	23	46
5	Merchandise Displayers	66	6	37
5	Personal Care Aides	78	26	31
5	Retail Salesperson	67	3	24
5	Sale Worker Supervisors	73	9	32
5	Sales Agents, Financial Services	72	8	41
5	Sales Representative Wholesale	68	9	42
5	Security Guards	80	27	21
5	Supervisors Of Food Preparation, Serving Workers	72	12	35
7	Installation, Maintenance, Repair Workers	69	21	44
7	Maintenance Worker	62	20	46
8	Heavy Truck And Tractor Drivers	45	9	31
8	Light Truck, Delivery Service Drivers	59	11	39
9	Janitors and Cleaners	49	13	36
9	Labourers	58	11	42
	Across occupations (all vacancies considered at once)	67	16	38

3.3 Specific results on cognitive skills

In this study, we considered five categories of cognitive skills (four ‘specific’ and one ‘generic’): computer skills, analytical skills, language skills, having a driving license and ability to learn. In contrast to education requirements, which were found in many job advertisements, cognitive skills appeared in less than one fourth of the vacancies across occupations. Nevertheless, there is a lot of variation - both across occupations and across the different cognitive skills examined. This confirms previous work of Kureková *et al.* (2012) and Kureková *et al.* (2015).

A closer look at the five sets of cognitive skills reveals that between 12% and 25% of the vacancies studied list computer skills, analytical skills or language skills (as is shown in Table 3.6). More specifically, 25% of the job advertisements refer to computer skills, 12% to analytical skills and 16% to language skills. Across the occupations, between 3% and 62% of the vacancies request computer skills, between 1% and 29% request analytical skills, and from 7% and 53% request language skills. Having a driving license and ability to learn are only mentioned in a very small share of vacancies.

The five occupations with the highest share of vacancies that refer to computer skills are the computer support specialists (62%), meeting, convention, event planners (57%), secretaries (53%), bookkeeping, accounting, auditing clerks (45%) and office clerks (44%). The occupations with the lowest percentages are cooks (3%), janitors and cleaners (5%), heavy truck and tractor drivers (5%), and light truck and delivery service drives (6%). These percentages, and the differences detected across occupations, are in line with the expectations of what the positions entail (in terms of tasks and responsibilities). As a result of technological progress, many ‘office jobs’ nowadays do require at least some level of computer skills. Over time, some of these skills may even become ‘*implicit skills*’ that will no longer be mentioned in a vacancy. There is a strong negative correlation of -0.63 between the ISCO code and the extent to which vacancies demand computer skills. This correlation implies that as jobs become more complicated and reach higher levels in the occupational hierarchy (a lower ISCO code), computer skills are more often listed.

When we turn to the analytical skills, we find that overall these skills are not so high in demand. There does appear to be some variation across the 30 occupations as depicted in Table 3.6, with the highest percentages reported for the tellers (29%), the sales agents - financial services (21%) and the bookkeeping, accounting, auditing clerks (20%).

Table 3.6 further presents the percentage of vacancies that refer to language skills across the 30 occupations. For 27 of the occupations, less than 25% of all job advertisements has language requirements. The percentage of advertisements that comprise language skills is higher for cooks (29%), security guards (38%) and meeting, convention and event planners (53%). Given that the United States has English as its main language, we expect that the language requirements in the vacancies mainly refer to the ability to speak and understand English (perhaps with the exception of the meeting, convention and event planners). In that sense, the results reported above are not very surprising.

Table 3.6 Share of vacancies referring to computer skills, analytical skills and language skills

ISCO	Occupation	Share with computer skills (%)	Share with analytical skills (%)	Share with language skills (%)
1	General and Operations Managers	32	14	17
2	Computer Support Specialists	62	16	9
2	HR Specialists	39	12	13
3	Bookkeeping, Accounting, Auditing Clerks	45	19	10
3	First-Line Office Supervisors	38	13	12
3	Medical Assistants	19	10	22
3	Meeting, Convention, Event Planners	57	1	53
3	Nursing Assistant	24	7	16
4	Cashiers	11	15	8
4	CS Representatives	35	8	18
4	Medical Secretaries	38	12	20
4	Office Clerks	44	12	15
4	Secretaries	53	13	15
4	Tellers	25	29	20
5	Combined Food Preparation Workers	8	4	14
5	Cooks, Restaurant	3	4	29
5	Merchandise Displayers	22	14	13
5	Personal Care Aides	9	8	13
5	Retail Salesperson	20	17	11
5	Sale Worker Supervisors	14	18	7
5	Sales Agents, Financial Services	22	21	16
5	Sales Representative Wholesale	26	7	16
5	Security Guards	11	15	38
5	Supervisors Of Food Preparation, Serving Workers	11	5	16
7	Installation, Maintenance, Repair Workers	23	12	9
7	Maintenance Worker	24	13	11
8	Heavy Truck And Tractor Drivers	5	5	10
8	Light Truck, Delivery Service Drivers	6	5	23
9	Janitors and Cleaners	5	5	17
9	Labourers	13	9	15
	Across occupations (all vacancies)	25	12	16

3.4 Summary

- US employers mention many qualifications in their job advertisements for the 30 most-frequently-advertised occupations, even for low- and medium-skilled positions. Yet, there is a positive relationship between the requirements listed and the complexity of the occupation: vacancies for more complex occupations contain more qualifications, as expected.
- The three qualifications that are found the most are: formal education (67% of the advertisements refer to it), service skills (49%) and experience (38%). There is some variation across the occupations examined but this does not affect this conclusion.
- Cognitive skills appear to be less important when all vacancies are considered at once (e.g. the most commonly found cognitive skill is 'computer skills', as mentioned in 20-30% of the vacancies), but are more relevant for a subset of occupations.
- Other requirements, such as having a driving license, are mentioned much less frequently

4. Case Study 3: 'The IT skills pyramid: a study on the demand for digital skills on the US labour market'

For our third case study, we use the same data as in the second case study but this time the focus is on *IT or digital skills*. Our interest in digital skills is motivated by the ongoing computerisation and its impact on the labour market. Our work is further inspired by a recent report produced by Burning Glass Technologies (BGT, 2015), which investigated the demand for digital skills for middle-skill jobs in the United States. In the report, three sets of digital skills were distinguished: *productivity software skills*, *advanced digital skills* and *occupation-specific digital skills* (which are skills that are specific to an occupation, e.g. nurses have to know how to use certain medical equipment). This distinction suggests a hierarchy between these categories, in which having acquired the productivity software skills is a prerequisite for acquiring the advanced digital skills. This hierarchy may also be reflected in the demand for these skills.

In our study, we further explore the idea of a hierarchy but we use a different approach to categorise digital skills. More specifically, we consider basic, intermediate and advanced digital skills and assess for each set how prevalent it is using a sample of 2 million vacancies for the 30 most-frequently-advertised occupations.¹ In comparison to the Burning Glass report (BGT, 2015), we add another layer of skills and broaden each of the different skills sets examined. *Basic digital skills* are not discussed in the Burning Glass report but we add them to our analysis because we also want to have a better understanding of how important basic IT skills such as computer, internet and email skills actually are. Moreover, adding this layer also allows us to look into general concepts, such as software and hardware. The second layer, the *intermediate digital skills*, corresponds to what the Burning Glass report labels 'productivity software skills'. In BGT (2015), the focus is on spreadsheets, word processing programmes and keywords such as MS Office and SAP. We consider word processing, spreadsheets, PowerPoint, office packages and SAP in this category, also examining different programmes that are associated with them (e.g. Microsoft Word, MS Excel). The top layer of the pyramid represents the *advanced digital skills*. In the Burning Glass study, these skills can be seen as higher-end computer networking skills. Jobs that call for such skills are not accessible to workers who do not possess them. Among the advanced digital skills in BGT (2015), there are four categories: customer relationship management (CRM), computer and network support (e.g. SQL, Linux), digital media and design (e.g. Adobe Acrobat), and social media tools and search engine analysis (e.g. blogs). In our work, we distinguish between 9 categories (CRM, databases and data management, data analysis and statistics, programming and programming languages, digital media and web design, desktop publishing, CMS (content management system), social media and blogging, and SEO (search engine optimisation)) and further examined buzz words like big data, cloud computing, etc.

As explained in more depth in the methodology report, we first create a list of *keywords* to capture each of the skills mentioned above and calculate - in total and by occupation - the share of job advertisements that contain these keywords. Our list of keywords is inspired by other academic and policy-relevant publications on the topic, as well as trade publications, information from specialised job portals, newspaper articles, blog posts and a variety of other sources. This list is not exhaustive

¹ Occupation-specific digital skills are not considered, as our interest lies in transversal IT skills.

but should nevertheless give us a better understanding of the demand for IT skills on the US labour market.

4.1 A comparison of the Burning Glass vacancies with the occupation tasks

As a first step in our analysis, we take a broad perspective and compare the tasks and skills described in the Burning Glass job advertisements with the tasks that are typically associated with the occupations they refer to. This information is extracted from existing occupational classifications, like ISCO and O*NET. In Figure 4.1, we present an example of this comparison for three occupations (one low-skilled, one medium-skilled, one high-skilled). In the figure, the *'word cloud'* is created on the basis of all vacancies available for the occupation. A word cloud is based on the 100 most-frequently mentioned words, corrected for punctuations, stop words (commonly used words in the English language), stemming, etc. By generating word clouds, we can shed some light on how important digital skills are - do they actually show up in the work clouds?

For the *low-skilled occupation*, janitors and cleaners, we notice that the list of tasks does not include any reference to IT-related skills. A similar picture emerges from the word clouds: the word cloud reflects the list of common tasks very well. Common words are experience, cleaning, clean, wipe, sweep, mop, sanitation etc. No IT skills are found. We then turn our attention to a *medium-skilled occupation*, medical secretary. This occupation was selected because it is a middle-skill jobs that does require IT skills. When we look at the list of tasks of a medical secretary, we notice that text processing is among the tasks mentioned (e.g. compiling reports, documents and correspondence, completing forms, maintaining files). Many of these tasks likely also involve spreadsheets (e.g. preparing financial statements, billing, drafting budgets). Other tasks that can be expected to be performed on a computer are scheduling and confirming appointments, communication with patients and staff (which could entail using scheduling software and email). Tasks related to data management and data entry seem likely as well. All the aforementioned tasks are reflected in the word cloud: the emphasis on the medical dimension is clear, with words such as health, medical, patient, care, hospital, etc. A second dimension that stands out is secretarial work, with words including clerical, administrative, scheduling, billing, communication, forms and office. The computer-related skills are reflected in computer, systems, data and programs. Finally, we consider a *high-skilled occupation*, the computer support specialists. This occupation is a typical IT-job and could have the highest demand for IT skills of all occupations in our sample. Moreover, it is likely that any specialised IT skills (or advanced digital skills) will also show up here. Among the list of tasks, we indeed spot several advanced digital skills, including management of operating systems and programming. We also find a number of general concepts, like hardware and software. The list of tasks is rather general and does not include specific programming languages or software. When we look at the word cloud, we find words such as computer, electronics, online, equipment, systems, software, access, technology, etc. We also find a number of words that highlight the customer-related dimension of this job, with client, support, and services as examples.

In addition to the word clouds, we have coded all tasks defined for the occupation (in ISCO and O*NET) as follows: for each task, we determined whether it *clearly requires IT skills*, *could require IT skills* (the task does not imply IT skills but it could be performed in such a way that IT skills could be used to carry it out), or *clearly does not require IT skills*. This coding exercise was carried out by two individual coders. Table 4.1 summarises the share of tasks requiring IT skills and compares it with the prevalence of IT skills in the vacancies (the correlation between these two measures is 0.6).

Table 4.1 Share of vacancies requiring IT skills and share of tasks associated that require IT skills

Occupation	IT skill requirement in vacancies (%)	Task may require IT skills (%)	Task certainly requires IT skills (%)
General and Operations Managers	32	58.620	0.000
HR Specialists	39	63.330	16.670
Meeting, Convention, Event Planners	57	82.140	0.000
Computer Support Specialists	62	25.000	75.000
Merch Displayers	22	10.000	3.330
Nursing Assistant	24	7.690	0.000
Medical Assistants	19	21.430	25.000
Security Guards	11	16.670	0.000
Supervisors of Food Prep, Serving Workers	11	22.220	0.000
Cooks, Restaurant	3	15.380	0.000
Combined Food Prep Workers	8	14.290	0.000
Janitors And Cleaners	5	7.410	0.000
Personal Care Aides	9	30.000	0.000
Sale Worker Supervisors	14	53.570	3.570
Cashiers	11	40.000	2.860
Retail Salesperson	20	48.280	0.000
Sales Agents, Financial Services	22	78.570	0.000
Sales Representative Wholesale	26	62.960	0.000
First-Line Office Supervisors	38	51.430	2.860
Bookkeeping, Accounting, Auditing Clerks	45	62.860	31.430
Tellers	25	61.760	20.590
CS Representatives	35	55.000	5.000
Medical Secretaries	38	62.500	16.670
Secretaries	53	52.500	30.000
Office Clerks	44	52.000	32.000
Maintenance Worker	24	16.220	0.000
Installation, Maintenance, Repair Workers	23	22.500	2.500
Heavy Truck And Tractor Drivers	5	2.700	5.410
Light Truck, Delivery Service Drivers	6	22.730	0.000
Labourers	13	0.000	0.000
Correlation with skill requirement		0.594	0.656

4.2 Basic and general digital skills

As a first step in the analysis, we focus on the prevalence of general IT-related concepts. In Table 4.2, we list the number and the percentage of vacancies in which these concepts are mentioned. In 690,922 of the 1,988,768 job advertisements in our sample, computer skills are requested (this is captured by the keyword ‘computer’). This corresponds to 34.74% of the vacancies. Across the occupations, this number ranges from 5% (personal care aides) to 92% (meeting, convention, event planners). Other occupations with a high demand for such skills are computer support specialists (65.02%), medical secretaries (58.29%) and merchandise displayers and office clerks (about 54%). Besides computer skills, we consider how many advertisements include general concepts such as software or hardware. 9.45% of the vacancies mentions the keyword software, while 2.75% refers to the keyword hardware. When it comes to internet, we find that 19% of the vacancies refers to internet skills. This share ranges from 6% to 60%. For email, the corresponding percentages are 22%, 7% and 93%.

Table 4.2 Number and share of vacancies in which general IT-related concepts such as computer, software, hardware, internet and email are demanded

	Number of vacancies	Percentage of vacancies	Max. across occupations (%)	Min. across occupations (%)
Computer	690,922	34.74	92.34	4.99
Software	187,850	9.45	37.46	1.51
Hardware	54,607	2.75	36.72	0.04
Internet/Web	379,021	19.06	59.55	6.02
Email/MS Outlook	434,975	21.87	93.05	7.07
* Email/Email	344,147	17.30	40.56	6.27
* MS Outlook	119,513	6.01	52.86	0.46

Table 4.3 lists the five occupations with the highest demand for the basic or general computer skills examined. In the table, the percentage of job advertisements for a specific occupation that refers to these skills are mentioned. There is a lot of variation, both across occupations for individual skills and across skills. Interestingly, some of the occupations appear in the top 5 for multiple skills. More precisely, computer support specialists, office clerks, secretaries and combined food preparation workers each appear three times. Cooks, janitors and cleaners, and customer service representatives appear twice.

Table 4.3 The five occupations with the highest demand for computer, software, hardware, internet and email knowledge or skills

	Computer	Software	Hardware	Internet	Email
1	Meeting, Convention, Event Planners (92%)	Secretaries (37%)	Combined Food Preparation Workers (37%)	CS Representatives (60%)	Combined Food Preparation Workers (93%)
2	Computer Support Specialists (65%)	Cooks, Restaurant (30%)	Secretaries (23%)	Combined Food Preparation Workers (45%)	Cooks, Restaurant (41%)
3	Medical Secretaries (58%)	Computer Support Specialists (24%)	CS Representatives (8%)	Secretaries (44%)	Office Clerks (33%)
4	Office Clerks (54%)	Office Clerks (21%)	Retail Salesperson (7%)	Tellers (29%)	Computer Support Specialists (31%)
5	Merchandise Displayers (54%)	Janitors And Cleaners (17%)	Installation, Maintenance, Repair Workers (6%)	Personal Care Aides (28%)	Janitors And Cleaners (28%)

In Figure 4.2, we compare our findings for low-skilled, medium-skilled and high-skilled in an IT skills pyramid. The pyramid has five horizontal slices, reflecting different skills, and three vertical slices, reflecting different sets of occupations (low-skilled on the left, medium-skilled in the middle, and high-skilled on the right). Horizontal slices show the percentage of vacancies that demand a certain skill or a set of skills, such as email and MS Outlook in the second slice. Regardless of the complexity of the occupations, the same skills appear in the same order: in all cases general computer skills are demanded the most, while software and hardware are only referred to in a handful of vacancies. In addition, a clear pattern emerges across occupations: the number of job advertisements that refer to basic or general computer skills is lower for the low- than for the medium-skilled occupations and lower for the medium- than for the high-skilled occupations.

Figure 4.2 The basic IT skills pyramid for occupations of different levels of complexity

4.3 Intermediate digital skills

When we focus on the intermediate digital skills, we devote special attention to word or text processing and spreadsheets - which were found to be particularly important in the Burning Glass study (BGT, 2015). The results of our analysis of the percentage of job advertisements that refer to intermediate digital skills are reported in Table 4.4. Almost 13% of the vacancies refer explicitly to word or text processing (this ranges between 1% and more than 50% across occupations), while spreadsheets appear in 14% (<1%-55%). About 3% of the job advertisements call for Microsoft PowerPoint, MS PowerPoint, etc. (here, we did not search for words such as present, presenting or presentations, because these very likely appear in nearly all vacancies). For individual occupations, this number varies between <1% and 20%. All of the aforementioned skills are typically included in standard office packages, and therefore we extend our search to also capture keywords such as MS Office, Open Office, Libre Office and so on. In 170,747 of the vacancies or 9%, an explicit reference to office packages is made. This number is as high as 31% for some occupations, and less than 1% for others. Note that 428,594 vacancies or 21.55% refers to at least one of the following keywords (but could include more than one as well): Text Processing, Spreadsheets, MS PowerPoint, or Office. To avoid double counting, we do not simply add the individual counts but instead go through all vacancies and include them when at least one of the keywords is found. 68% of the job listings comprises

at least one of the keywords mentioned so far. Finally, a last type of intermediate digital skills that we examine is SAP, which is found in 1% of the vacancies when all job advertisements are considered at once (0%-<5%).

Table 4.4 Overview of the intermediate digital skills

	Number of vacancies	Percentage of vacancies	Max. across occupations (%)	Min. across occupations (%)
Word/Text Processing	255,660	12.86	54.30	1.02
* Word Processing/Text/Processing	47,794	2.40	16.37	0.11
* MS Word/Word	255,638	12.85	54.30	1.02
Spreadsheet/MS Excel	287,848	14.47	54.53	0.47
* Spreadsheet	52,995	2.66	18.07	0.04
* MS Excel/Excel	256,906	12.92	54.27	0.44
MS PowerPoint	53,540	2.69	19.88	0.03
MS Office/Open Office/Libre Office	170,747	8.59	31.39	0.38
SAP	20,171	1.01	5.39	0.01

Table 4.5 presents for each of the intermediate digital skills the five occupations with the highest demand, i.e. the five occupations with the highest shares of advertisements that call for these skills. As before, there are several occupations that appear to be rather demanding when it comes to intermediate digital skills. Computer support specialists and office clerks, for example, appear in four out of the five cases (for the former PowerPoint is missing, for the latter SAP is missing).

Table 4.5 The five occupations with the highest demand for different intermediate digital skills

	Text Processing	Spreadsheets	PowerPoint	Office	SAP
1	Combined Food Preparation Workers (54%)	Combined Food Preparation Workers (55%)	Cooks, Restaurant (20%)	Cooks, Restaurant (32%)	Computer Support Specialists (5%)
2	Cooks, Restaurant (51%)	Cooks, Restaurant (51%)	Janitors And Cleaners (8%)	Office Clerks (22%)	Labourers (3%)
3	Office Clerks (37%)	Computer Support Specialists (47%)	Office Clerks (7%)	Janitors And Cleaners (21%)	Cooks, Restaurant (2%)
4	Computer Support Specialists (33%)	Office Clerks (34%)	Bookkeeping, Accounting, Auditing Clerks (5%)	Computer Support Specialists (21%)	Janitors And Cleaners (2%)
5	Janitors And Cleaners (26%)	Janitors And Cleaners (28%)	General and Operations Managers (5%)	Cashiers (19%)	Medical Secretaries (2%)

We then distinguish low-, medium- and high-skilled occupations to verify whether any differences can be detected in terms of intermediate digital skills. This comparison is presented in a skill pyramid (Figure 4.3). There is a similar pattern as before: the share of vacancies that request specific intermediate digital skills is the largest for high-skilled occupations and the lowest for low-skilled ones, while medium-skilled occupations are found in the middle. This pattern is found for text processing, spreadsheets and office packages. On the other hand, SAP is mentioned the most often among the low-skilled occupations - though the differences with the other groups are minor. For PowerPoint, the differences are also minor but here we detect the highest share for the medium-skilled occupations. For low-skilled occupations, text processing seems more relevant than spreadsheets while the

opposite holds for medium- and high-skilled occupations. Also, SAP and PowerPoint have changed positions with regards to the medium- and high-skilled occupations.

Figure 4.3 The intermediate IT skills pyramid for occupations of different levels of complexity

4.4 Advanced digital skills

In our study, we investigate 9 classes of advanced digital skills: CRM (customer relationship management), databases and data management, data analysis and statistics, programming and programming languages, digital media and web design, desktop publishing, CMS (content management system), social media and blogging, and SEO (search engine optimisation.) The list of keywords that is used to identify each of these categories is presented in Figure 4.4. For each category, we search for the general concepts (e.g. social networks) and specific programs that are commonly used (e.g. Twitter).

Figure 4.4 List of keywords used to identify advanced digital skills. On the left, the name of the aggregated category is mentioned. On the right, the keywords associated with the category are shown

CRM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •CRM •customer relationship management
Databases & data management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Database, data base, database management, data base management, data management, data entry, data warehouse •SQL, Microsoft Acces, MS Access, Access
Data analysis & statistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Data analysis, data processing, statistics •Stata, EViews, SAS, SPSS, Matlab
Programming & programming languages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Programming, programming language •C++, C+, C++ program, C+ program, Python, Java, Ruby, Perl, PHP, Fortran, Visual Basic, VBA.net, Javascript
Digital media & web design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Digital media, digital design, web design, web page design, web development •Illustrator, InDesign, Photoshop, CSS
Desktop publishing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Desktop publishing •Microsoft Publish, MS Publish, Visual Studio
CMS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •CMS, content management system, client mangament system, customer relationship management, contact management system •Drupal, Plone, Joomla
Social media & blogging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Social media, social network, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn •Blog, WordPress
SEO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •SEO, search engine optimisation •Google Analytics

Table 4.6 reports for each of the advanced digital skills the number and percentage of job advertisements that list them, as well as the minimum and maximum shares across occupations. One of the most striking results presented in the table is that very few vacancies refer to advanced digital skills: for five of the categories, less than 1% of the vacancies refer to any of the keywords. For three other categories, the share is below 3%. Only for one category, which is databases and data management, over 10% of the job advertisements make reference to any of the keywords examined (12% to be precise). By listing both the counts for the aggregated categories and for individual keywords, we get more insight into the composition of these categories. Aggregated categories are constructed by counting all job advertisements that refer to at least one of the keywords mentioned in the subgroups.

Another important result is that for some of the advanced digital skills, the variation across occupations is huge. This applies particularly to databases and data management (the minimum value is 1%, the maximum is equal to 39%) and programming and programming languages (the minimum is 1%, the maximum is 21%). For the remaining advanced digital skills, smaller divergences are detected. Examples are data analysis and statistics (0.15%-8.94%), social media and blogging (0.41%-6.71%).

Table 4.6 Advanced digital skills, the keywords in bold refer to aggregated categories

Advanced digital skills	Number of vacancies	Percentage of vacancies	Max. across occupations (%)	Min. across occupations (%)
CRM	17,639	0.89	4.08	0.03
Databases & data management	232,160	11.67	38.63	1.25
* Database, data base, data/database/ data base management, data entry, data warehouse	173,315	8.71	34.25	0.32
* MS Access	70,504	3.55	36.21	0.11
* SQL	2,405	0.12	3,30	0,01
Data analysis & statistics	39,662	1.99	8.94	0.15
* Data analytics/processing, statistics	39,242	1.97	8.86	0.14
* EViews	2	0.00	0.00	0.00
* Stata	a	0.00	0.01	0.00
* SAS	423	0.02	0.11	0.00
* Matlab	20	0.00	0.01	0.00
* SPSS	117	0.01	0.06	0.00
Programming & programming languages	31,127	1.57	21.19	0.17
* Programming language, programmer	679	0.03	0.47	0.00
* Programming	18,272	0.92	5.76	0.00
* Python	282	0.01	0.28	0.00
* Ruby	250	0.01	0.11	0.00
* Fortran	8	0.00	0.01	0.00
* Visual Basic, VBA.NET	407	0.02	0.52	0.00
* Java	974	0.05	0.94	0.00
* PhP	5,747	0.29	0.69	0.09
* C+/C++ program	23,411	1.18	20.86	0.01
* Perl	289	0.01	0.31	0.00
* JavaScript	370	0.02	0.26	0.00
Digital media & web design	7,293	0.37	1.91	0.02
* Digital media/design	506	0.03	0.12	0.00
* Web/web page design, web development	1,827	0.09	1.01	0.01
* Illustrator	569	0.03	0.13	0.00
* InDesign	553	0.03	0.23	0.00
* Photoshop	1,219	0.06	0.40	0.00
* CSS	3,642	0.18	0.93	0.01
Desktop publishing	2,188	0.11	1.13	0.00
* Desktop publishing	1,678	0.08	0.91	0.00
* MS Publish	482	0.02	0.25	0.00
* Visual Studio	61	0.00	0.10	0.00
CMS	11,574	0.58	4.64	0.01
* Content/client/customer/contact management system	11,354	0.57	4.64	0.01
* Drupal	133	0.01	0.05	0.00
* Joomla	141	0.01	0.05	0.00
* Plone	8	0.00	0.00	0.00
Social media & blogging	53,569	2.69	6.71	0.41
* Social media, social network	13,439	0.68	3.64	0.07
* Facebook	27,021	1.36	3.54	0.23
* LinkedIn	21,045	1.06	3.69	0.17
* Twitter	20,769	1.04	2.39	0.21
* Blog	5,716	0.29	3.06	0.01
* Word Press	468	0.02	0.23	0.00
SEO	429	0.02	0.20	0.00
* SEO, search engine, optimisation	406	0.02	0.20	0.00
* Google Analytics	39	0.00	0.03	0.00

We then investigate in which occupations the advanced digital skills that appear in at least 1% of the job advertisements are the most highly requested (i.e. the most frequently mentioned). Results are reported in Table 4.7. Many of the occupations that show up in the table are typical medium- to high-skilled white-collar office jobs. In Table 4.7, we find four occupations that appear more than once: HR specialist (four times), secretary (three times), office clerk (two times) and bookkeeping, accounting, auditing clerks (two times). General concepts typically receive much more counts than the individual programs listed. Then, we zoom in on four occupations that have relatively high demands for the advanced digital skills: secretaries, HR specialists, computer support specialists and office clerks. Figure 4.5 presents a brief overview of which advanced digital skills matter most for these occupations.

Table 4.7 The five occupations with the highest demand for different advanced digital skills. Only skills that appear in at least 1% of total vacancies are listed

	Databases & data management	Data analysis & statistics	Programming & programming languages	Social media & blogging
1	Secretary (39%)	Secretary (9%)	Security Guard (21%)	HR Specialist (7%)
2	Meeting, Convention, Event Planner (37%)	Office Clerk (7%)	Computer Support Specialist (3%)	Sales Representative Wholesale (5%)
3	Office Clerk (36%)	Bookkeeping, Accounting, Auditing Clerk (6%)	HR Specialist (3%)	Nursing Assistant (5%)
4	HR Specialist (33%)	HR Specialist (6%)	Secretary (2%)	Personal Care Aide (4%)
5	Bookkeeping, Accounting, Auditing Clerk (31%)	First-Line Office Supervisor (5%)	Maintenance Worker (2%)	Sales Agent, Financial Services (4%)

Figure 4.5 Focus on the advanced digital skills demanded in four occupations

4.5 Skills mismatches

We concluded our analysis by going back to the list of tasks that we coded to further our understanding of skill mismatch. More specifically, for each of the tasks that could or does require IT skills, we examined which precise IT skills are implied (e.g. instead of thinking about ‘computer skills’, we looked into ‘text processing’ or ‘data management’). This revised list of tasks was then compared with the share of advertisements requiring those specific IT skills to identify potential mismatches. A mismatch was *defined as a situation in which either the share of vacancies that call for a specific skill is very high but this is not clear from the list of tasks, or vice versa*. On the basis of this approach, we identified 16 occupations with a mismatch (see Table 4.8 and 4.9). In ten cases, the mismatch was of the latter category. For example, bank tellers’ tasks heavily involve working with databases but there does not seem to be much explicit demand for data skills in the job advertisements for this occupation. five occupations had relatively high requirement of a specific IT skill, which does not seem to be related to any of the tasks for that occupation.

Interestingly, the mismatch where the skill was required according to the task but not mentioned explicitly in the job advertisements is linked to basic IT skills, such as email, which suggests that those are sometimes assumed implicitly. The opposite case relates to advanced digital skills, such as computer programming, which potentially point to a technologically-driven up-skilling of occupations.

Table 4.8 Comparison of density of IT skills requirement in vacancies and IT skills requirements associated with tasks relevant for specific occupations. Mismatches are indicated in grey. Results for internet, social media and blogging, email and software

Occupation	Internet		Social media & blogging		Email		Software	
Bookkeeping, Accounting, Auditing Clerks	1	17.34	0	2.42	1	31.43	1	24.21
Cashiers	1	12.67	0	0.41	1	7.07	1	2.46
Combined Food Prep Workers	0	6.02	0	1.07	1	11.52	1	1.95
Computer Support Specialists	1	43.98	0	2.89	1	27.16	1	37.46
Cooks, Restaurant	0	8.32	0	1.48	1	16.77	0	1.81
CS Representatives	1	19.2	0	2.24	1	26.11	1	12.13
First-Line Office Supervisors	1	17.11	1	3.34	1	26.26	1	13.74
General and Operations Managers	1	14.3	1	3.14	1	24.14	1	11.64
Heavy Truck And Tractor Drivers	1	10.2	0	1.5	1	15.23	1	2.06
HR Specialists	1	23.75	1	6.71	1	28.47	1	17.04
Janitors And Cleaners	0	12.12	0	3.67	1	16.71	0	1.99
Labourers	0	8.81	0	1.58	0	17.19	0	4.48
Light Truck, Delivery Service Drivers	0	9.49	0	1.84	1	13.58	1	2.76
Maintenance Worker	1	13.89	0	2.1	1	20.24	1	9.36
Medical Assistants	0	14.76	0	2.57	1	15.17	1	9.34
Medical Secretaries	1	10.08	0	2.9	1	20.61	1	15.71
Meeting, Convention, Event Planners	1	45.41	1	0.88	1	93.05	0	1.51
Merch Displayers	0	59.55	0	1.11	0	27.65	1	12.33
Nursing Assistant	0	8.49	0	4.89	1	12.28	1	3.28
Office Clerks	1	21.56	0	2.97	1	33.05	1	21.2
Personal Care Aides	0	11.27	0	4.11	1	15.12	1	3.59
Retail Salesperson	1	27.99	0	2.81	1	14.19	1	3.37
Sale Worker Supervisors	1	10.81	0	2.06	1	16.8	1	4.03
Sales Agents, Financial Services	1	12.3	0	3.91	1	13.49	1	12.21
Sales Representative Wholesale	1	23.98	0	5	1	27.91	1	9.08
Secretaries	1	22.89	1	3.42	1	41.41	1	29.59
Security Guards	0	29.47	0	0.98	1	11.32	0	2.59
Supervisors Of Food Prep, Serving Workers	1	8.66	0	2.63	0	15.2	1	5.62
Tellers	1	9.81	0	1.73	1	20.96	1	5.54

Table 4.9 Comparison of density of IT skills requirement in vacancies and IT skills requirements associated with tasks relevant for specific occupations. Mismatches are indicated in grey. Results for word processing, spreadsheets, databases and data management, and programming and programming languages

Occupation	Word processing		Spreadsheets		Databases & data management		Programming & program. Languages	
Bookkeeping, Accounting, Auditing Clerks	1	32.75	1	47.23	1	31.45	0	1.01
Cashiers	1	3.11	1	2.69	1	2.49	0	0.34
Combined Food Prep Workers	1	2.63	1	2.41	0	2.21	0	0.60
Computer Support Specialists	1	13.72	1	13.5	1	19.47	1	3.11
Cooks, Restaurant	1	2.94	1	3.4	1	2.17	0	0.60
CS Representatives	1	15.01	1	15.59	1	17.31	0	0.68
First-Line Office Supervisors	1	21.97	1	24.47	1	14.3	0	1.40
General and Operations Managers	1	18.03	1	19.76	1	6.05	0	0.90
Heavy Truck And Tractor Drivers	0	2.35	0	1.13	0	1.73	0	0.54
HR Specialists	1	26.35	1	27.97	1	33.46	0	2.93
Janitors And Cleaners	0	4.07	0	1.79	0	1.25	0	0.60
Labourers	0	4.78	0	5.28	0	7.04	0	0.33
Light Truck, Delivery Service Drivers	1	2.87	1	1.63	0	3.13	0	0.37
Maintenance Worker	1	10.42	1	9.46	1	5.37	0	2.10
Medical Assistants	1	7.33	1	5.11	1	11.79	0	1.18
Medical Secretaries	1	19.79	1	15.04	1	22.5	0	1.30
Meeting, Convention, Event Planners	1	54.3	1	54.53	0	37.47	0	0.22
Merch Displayers	1	8.34	1	20.9	1	15.23	0	0.17
Nursing Assistant	1	2.96	1	1.08	1	3.69	0	0.64
Office Clerks	1	36.8	1	33.83	1	35.51	0	1.54
Personal Care Aides	1	1.02	1	0.47	1	6.14	0	1.26
Retail Salesperson	1	5.19	1	14.51	1	3.73	0	0.51
Sale Worker Supervisors	1	7.12	1	6.75	1	4.29	0	0.52
Sales Agents, Financial Services	1	7.67	1	8.68	1	6.85	0	0.56
Sales Representative Wholesale	1	13.68	1	16.47	1	13.66	0	0.47
Secretaries	1	50.51	1	50.77	1	38.63	0	2.13
Security Guards	1	3.85	0	2.65	0	7.81	0	21.19
Supervisors Of Food Prep, Serving Workers	1	9.3	1	5.95	1	3.14	0	0.40
Tellers	1	3.65	1	3.62	1	1.42	0	0.44

4.6 Summary

- About 35% of the job advertisements of a sample of close to twomillion vacancies for the 30 most-frequently-advertised occupations in the US calls for computer skills. This number is particularly interesting, as it implies that there are jobs for which computer skills are not a prerequisite to carry out the work (despite the computerisation of many occupations), while at the same time for other jobs computer skills have already developed into implicit skills. Interestingly, when looking into specific occupations, there is a lot of variation (meaning that requests for computer skills range from 'rare' to 'universal').
- The analysis also points to a clear hierarchy: basic digital skills are relatively widespread across the occupations, while advanced digital skills are rare. For intermediate digital skills, the conclusion is reached that these can be found for many occupations, especially white-collar office jobs. Regardless of the types of IT skills, a clear pattern emerges: IT skills are much more requested in vacancies for high-skilled than for medium- and low-skilled occupations, and similarly more for medium- than for low-skilled occupations.
- Within the basic digital skills, especially 'computer skills', 'internet' and 'email' are particularly relevant. These skills are widespread among low-skilled occupations as well as the other twocategories. Even for high- and medium-skilled occupations, these skills are mentioned in the vacancies.
- For the intermediate digital skills, text/word processing and spreadsheets are most relevant. Having these skills can be regarded as an 'entry ticket' to medium- and high-skilled jobs.
- When it comes to the advanced digital skills, especially databases are relevant. Even for high-skilled jobs, these skills are mentioned fairly infrequently.

5. Case Study 4: ‘An occupations observatory’

(Beblavý et al., 2016d)

In the fourth case study, we piloted a new methodology to identify new and emerging occupations, which is based on the meta data available on job portals and the tag system that portals use to structure their vacancies, in particular. For 11 countries,² we selected a job board and kept track of the new occupation tags that were added over a six-month period. Online job portals use occupation tags to organise job advertisements so that job seekers can easily navigate the website and find similar vacancies. Occupation tags often are stored in a database. Few portals publish their list of tags online.

As explained in detail in the methodological report, our proposed approach to identify new and emerging occupations involves searching for new tags that are added to the job portal’s occupational classification. For each country, it delivers a list of tags that can be compared over time. Our approach consists of three steps: establishing the benchmark (by collecting an initial list of occupation tags), collecting data (i.e. newly added tags were extracted, cleaned and translated – on a monthly basis) and analysing the data. The underlying idea is to extract newly added occupation tags, evaluate whether they indeed refer to a new or emerging occupation, add them to the benchmark, and then repeat the process. If an occupation tag clearly does not refer to a new or emerging occupation, it is added to the benchmark but no further steps are taken. If, in contrast, the tag could refer to a new or emerging occupation, it is examined in more depth (e.g. by checking available vacancies on other job boards, presence in occupational classification). For this examination, we also rely on job vacancies to complete any missing information.

The results of our approach are summarised in an *occupation card*. For each potentially new or emerging occupation, we produce an occupation card that combines information from different sources: the vacancy that accompanies the newly added tag, the portal on which it was found, similar job advertisements on other online job boards, the existing occupational classifications, Google Trends, etc. By filling in an occupation card, one has a very clear idea of whether an occupation indeed is new or emerging, as it that provide details on the identification process, tasks, requirements and prevalence, link with the existing occupational classifications and so on. All occupation cards will be assembled in an ‘*Occupations Observatory*’.

5.1 Structure of an occupation card

Each occupation card has *six main sections*, which deal with different topics. Section 5.2.1.1 deals with ‘*identification*’. It describes where the occupation, its corresponding vacancy and tag, were found. To this end, information is provided on when the job advertisement was published, on which job board, for which country and sector, etc. As a second step, the card provides more details on the vacancy, by listing the job description and profile, and any other tags that were linked to the vacancy. Section 5.2.1.1 captures the time and space dimensions of an occupation, which are relevant to be able to evaluate whether it truly is new or emerging. Section 5.2.1.1 also briefly recalls the aim of the occupation card and the methodology used to compile it.

² The 11 countries are: Belgium, the Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Slovakia, Spain and the UK.

For example, Section 5.2.1.1 could mention that a tag for OSS/BSS specialist was found on profesia.sk on 2 September 2015. We would also go back to the advertisement that triggered the new tag and look at the information available in the vacancy (type of employer, industry, job description, profile, portal tags).

The second section of an occupation card is Section 5.2.1.2, which covers ‘*definition*’ as well as ‘*tasks and responsibilities*’. For example, one of the tags that was added to the Slovak job board in our pilot was ‘OSS/BSS’. In Section 5.2.1.2, an explanation would then be offered on what OSS/BSS means and whether it is related to any existing occupations. The latter is important because new or emerging occupations typically evolve out of existing ones. Section 5.2.1.2 also discusses the prevalence of the occupation in the country on whose job board it was found and presents details on the responsibilities and tasks involved (using information from other job portals).

For example, Section 5.2.1.2 would provide a definition of OSS/BSS, explain whether this occupation is related to any existing occupations, and consider its prevalence in Slovakia (are there similar vacancies on the same/other job portals or via a web search). It also comprises an overview of the tasks and responsibilities of an OSS/BSS specialist, e.g. validate and write code.

Section 5.2.1.3 is devoted to the ‘*requirements*’ that come with the occupation, with a focus on formal education, cognitive and non-cognitive skills and experience in particular. In our pilot, this information was derived from the vacancies available for the occupation. By assessing requirements for an occupation, we can get more insight into whether it is linked to other occupations (e.g. as their requirements are relatively similar) and how different it actually is.

For example, in Slovakia, an OSS/BSS specialist is expected to tertiary education, previous experience with IT, JAVA, SQL, C++ and other programs, knowledge of telecommunications, communication skills, and so on. Many vacancies also list non-cognitive skills, such as detail-oriented, self-motivated, ambitious and other skills.

In the fourth section, Section 5.2.1.4, the analysis carried out to complete Sections 5.2.1.2 and 5.2.1.3 is *extended to other countries (within and outside of Europe)*. The aim of this exercise is to determine whether the occupation is new and emerging in one country only, whether it already exists elsewhere, and what differences there are across the countries. This comparison is further complemented with a Google Trends analysis of whether the occupation is on the rise or in decline, and in which countries.

For example, is the position of an OSS/BSS specialist is only new in Slovakia or does it also exist in other countries? For Belgium, on the basis of a search on Google and job portals, we find occupations similar to that of the online marketing coordinator in Europe and the US. We also consider whether the tasks and requirements are similar in these countries.

Section 5.2.1.5 bridges the gap between our methodology and the traditional approach to capture new and emerging occupations by verifying whether the occupation is present in the existing *occupational classifications* (both national and international).

For example, for Belgium, we aimed to find the occupation of an online marketing coordinator in different occupational classifications. We could not find it in ISCO and ESCO, nor in the classification of many European countries. However, a similar occupation was found in the national classification of Italy, Poland and Germany, and the United States.

The final section, Section 5.2.1.6, *summarises the conclusions of our analysis*. It discusses whether the occupation is indeed new or emerging and what its impact on education and training could be. Section 5.2.1.6 covers the country where the occupation was found, the European level and the global level.

As a further illustration, we present occupation cards for two potentially new or emerging occupations (online marketing coordinator and drug safety specialist). Other examples can be found in Beblavý *et al.* (2016d).

5.2 First example of an occupation card: 'Online Marketing Coordinator'

5.2.1 Occupation Card 1: Online Marketing Coordinator

Date: 30 September 2015

5.2.1.1 Identification

The identification of new occupations, such as the Online Marketing Coordinator presented in the current document, is based on an innovative methodology that we are piloting here. This methodology is embedded in the rapidly growing strand of the literature that relies on web-based data sources to conduct labour market research (see Askitas & Zimmermann, 2015). The main idea behind our methodology is to identify new occupations via the *occupational classification* that online job portals use to guide job seekers on their website. Typically, such occupational classifications have - at their core - a *tag system*, i.e. a list of tags that is used to assign vacancies to specific job categories. This list of tags can be published online or stored in a library accessed by an API search when a job seeker enters a word in the search box. Earlier research suggests that job portals tend to regularly update their list of tags to account for the emergence of new occupations and the disappearance of redundant ones.

In our pilot study, we focus on 11 countries for which we keep track of one of their main online job portals. For these countries, we created a *benchmark*, which is composed of their occupational classification (their list of tags) on 30 June 2015. Our goal is to determine whether this tag system could also be used to identify new occupations, by comparing the benchmark classification with the *current occupational classification* of the portal at regularly intervals, i.e. every month. The *tags that are not yet included* in the benchmark, i.e. missing from the list of tags when the benchmark and the new list of tags are compared, could point to new or emerging occupations. For more details on our methodology, we refer to the *Methodological Note* that is available on the website in the Occupations Observatory.

In the beginning of *August 2015*, a new tag was added to the *Belgian* online job board in our pilot. This tag was picked up (either via the API or via a web crawling technique that extracts the list of tags - this depends on the portal) and stored in a database. We then searched for an actual vacancy for an *online marketing coordinator* on this portal (to discover what triggered the new tag). More details on this tag/vacancy can be found below; these details cover (i) the portal to which the tag was added and on which the vacancy was found, and (ii) the content of the sample vacancy that we study in more depth (to identify tasks and responsibilities - skills and other requirements).

Details on the tag and the job advertisement	
When did the tag/vacancy appear online?	July 2015
On which online job board was the tag/vacancy published?	vacature.com
Which country is covered by this job portal?	Belgium (Flanders)
In which industry is the employer active?	Broad (no specific industry listed)
What type of employer has posted the vacancy?	Private company

Sample job advertisement	
Job description (responsibilities and tasks of the job)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Responsible for (co-)planning, implementation, monitoring and online publication of online digital marketing communication - Responsible for various online tools such as websites, email, apps and social pages - Detect the needs of sales force, come up with inspiring new ideas, present company's message in a simple and attractive way - Work smoothly together with colleagues and external partners - Report to the senior marketing coordinator
Job profile (education, skills and other requirements for the job)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least a bachelor's/master's degree or equivalent by experience - Digital native bitten by the online microbe; always following the latest trends - Can use CMS systems and WordPress, understands the basics of HTML and has good knowledge of SEO, SEA, Google Analytics - Has good writing skills (NL/EN) and communicates fluently - Stress-resistant, result-oriented, enjoys working on many projects at once
Job portal tags (tags attached to the vacancy on the job board)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Function group: web application developer, database marketing - Function: online marketing coordinator; marketing; online marketing; eMarketing; eMarketing; marketer; eMarketeer; digital marketing; digital marketer; online marketer; social media; social - Sector: general industry - Employment type: fixed position, working time 36-40 hours per week - Education level: Professional Bachelor - Experience: 1-2 years of experience

5.2.1.2 Definition, responsibilities and tasks

A. Definition

What is 'Online Marketing'?

Online marketing is a form of marketing and advertising that relies on the Internet to deliver promotional marketing messages to consumers. The concept includes email marketing, search engine marketing (SEM), social media marketing, mobile advertising and display advertising, e.g. web banner advertising. The concept of online marketing is also known as *Internet advertising* or *online advertising*. Online advertising is widely used across virtually all sectors.

Similarly to other forms of marketing, online marketing commonly involves a *publisher* (who integrates ads into its online content) and an *advertiser* (who provides ads to be displayed with the publisher's content). Other agents that could be involved are *advertising agencies* (who generate and place the ad copy), an *ad server* (who technologically delivers the ad and tracks statistics), and *advertising affiliates* (who are responsible for independent promotional work for the advertiser).

Some examples of related job titles: 'online marketing experts/assistants', 'online marketers', 'eMarketing specialist', 'online marketing and sales support'

More information on the occupation can be found on the Wikipedia pages:

- covering *online advertising* (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Online_advertising);
- covering *digital marketing* (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_marketing).

Is this position related to any existing occupations?

At first sight, the position of an online marketing coordinator appears to **combine** some of the tasks and responsibilities of other *marketing, advertising, sales or communication occupations* and those of occupations in the field of *information and communication technologies*.

Note that the concept of online marketing is closely related to that of *digital marketing*. Digital marketing is the 'targeted, measureable and interactive marketing of products or services using digital

technologies to reach and convert leads into customers. Its objective is to promote brands, build preference and increase sales through various digital marketing techniques, mainly using the Internet as a core promotional medium.’ The term emerged in the 1990s, but the concept only started to grow in 2000-10. Digital marketing includes, but is not limited to, email direct marketing, social media marketing, search engine optimisation or marketing, e-commerce marketing, content marketing/automation, influencer marketing, and mobile marketing. Online and digital marketing seem to overlap to some extent.

How prevalent is the occupation of an Online Marketing Coordinator in Belgium?

We looked for similar occupations on several job portals and did a Google search. Results of this exercise:

Job portals

- vacature.com: offers 11 vacancies for ‘online marketing’ and 9 for ‘digital marketing’.
- jobat.be: offers about 30 job ads for ‘online marketing’ and ‘digital marketing’.
- bloovi.be: offers about 35 related job advertisements.
- monster.be: offers about 16 job advertisements for ‘online marketer’.
- creativeskills.be: about 5 job advertisements published during the summer.
- careerjet.be: about 67 job advertisements for ‘digital marketing’.

Google Search (limited to .be websites):

- ‘online marketing vacature’: about 110,000 results.
- ‘online marketing job’: about 165,000 results.
- ‘internet marketing vacature’: about 63,700 results.
- ‘internet marketing job’: about 189,000 results.
- ‘digital marketing vacature’: about 23,300 results.
- ‘digital marketing job’: about 81,200 results.

B. What are the responsibilities and tasks of an online marketing coordinator?

This information is obtained from a sample of job vacancies, extracted from job portals (for Belgium).

- Responsibilities and tasks are generally *closely related to those of other marketing occupations*, i.e. other marketing, advertising, sales or communication occupations, such as initiation and implementation of offline and online campaigns and initiatives, but there is a lot more emphasis on the ‘online’ dimension here.
- Some vacancies focus on ‘*online marketing*’ and only include tasks and responsibilities related to marketing; other vacancies are looking for a *broader profile* and list tasks and responsibilities that are related to offline marketing, sales, web design, and other tasks.
- Development of an *online marketing, advertising and sales* strategy, which involves online branding, marketing activities and campaigns, generate traffic to websites, sending out newsletters.
- Implementation of *applications* (mobile, SMS), attract new followers, generate traffic to applications.
- Development of a *social media strategy*, which involves online branding, advertising activities, attracting new followers, organic search optimisation (via creating content, communication strategy), running a blog.

5.2.1.3 Education, skills and other requirements

This information is obtained from a sample of vacancies, extracted from job portals (for Belgium)

Formal education required	
Is formal education required?	Yes
Level of education	Tertiary education: bachelor's or master's degree
Field of education	Some vacancies require training in marketing, new media communications; other vacancies do not specify a field of education

Skills required	
Communication skills	Writing and communication skills, language skills (e.g. Dutch, French, English, German), copywriting
Computer skills	SEM, SEO, SEA, HTML, MS Office, Google Analytics, social media, web design, Web2.0, Photoshop, Dreamweaver, InDesign
Non-cognitive skills	Analytical thinking, self-motivated, takes initiative, entrepreneurial mind-set, problem-solving, result-oriented, team player, organised, customer friendly, flexible, dynamic
Occupation-specific skills	Understanding online marketing (content, campaigns), knowledge of online customer behaviour, planning, conception and optimisation of campaigns, eMarketing techniques, communication strategy, interest in what is happening online

Experience required	
Is experience required?	This depends on the level of the position in the firm (executive, assistant, ...): e.g. 1-2 years, 3-5 years, 5+ years
Is job-related experience required?	Yes, in some vacancies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - experience in online marketing activities and campaigns, sales-driven organisations, e-commerce - experience in the sector, e.g. tourism

5.2.1.4 Geographical prevalence

A. European perspective

Results from [job portals](#) and [Google search](#) for countries in different parts of Europe:

Some of the job portals consulted: Indeed, Monster, Stepstone, ...

Similar vacancies in Western Europe	
France	<i>Chargé de mission commercial et marketing, Chargé de Marketing Digital, Responsable Web Marketing, E-marketeur</i>
Germany	<i>Onlinemarketing-Manager/in, Mitarbeiter (m/w) im Onlinemarketing (SEA) für den Webshop, Junior Marketing Manager im Online-Bereich, Trainee Kreation Onlinemarketing (m/w), Vollzeit, E-Commerce)</i>
The Netherlands	<i>Online Marketeer, Marketing Assistant, Digital Marketing & e-Commerce Consultant, Marketeer/SEO specialist</i>
UK	<i>Digital Marketing Manager, Digital Marketing Analyst, Online Marketing Executive, Web and Digital Marketing Apprentice, Online Marketing Coordinator</i>
Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as the vacancies for Belgium? YES	<p>Tasks/Responsibilities: developing and implementing a marketing or sales strategy, branding, web design, online promotion, email marketing, content creation and management for website, social media platforms, newsletters, create statistics and reports, keeping up-to-date with technological advancements, proofreading, target group identification, budget planning, graphic design</p> <p>Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - bachelor's degree, previous experience in similar roles - knowledge of digital marketing, SEO, SEM, HTML, CSS, PHP, Adobe Photoshop or Illustrator, OM tools (Google Analytics, Adwords certificates required, Facebook), reporting results, able to develop a strategy, community management, written, verbal communication and presentation skills, English and other languages, data analysis, affinity with Internet/technology/IT - independent, dynamic, responsible, interested in the field, timeliness, creativity, enthusiastic, open-minded, focused, well-organised, commercial awareness, eager to learn, goal-oriented

Similar vacancies in Southern Europe	
Italy	<i>Responsabile Marketing e Web Marketing, Web Marketing Specialist, Online marketing manager, Impiegato web marketing, Addetto web marketing, Web Marketing Assistant</i>
Spain	<i>Especialista en Marketing Digital/E-commerce, Digital Marketing & SEM Executive, e-Commerce Marketing Manager, Responsable de Marketing Digital, Digital Marketing & Communication Support</i>
Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as the vacancies for Belgium? YES	<p>Tasks/Responsibilities: development and execution of marketing strategies, creation of advertising campaigns, branding, email marketing, management of and content creation for website, social media, newsletters, creation of all business graphics and materials (also offline), attract traffic to platforms, data analysis and reporting, copywriting, coordinate communication/sales strategy</p> <p>Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - bachelor's degree, experience in related field or position - knowledge of marketing, social media, database management and CRM, marketing tools, analytical skills, computer skills (including programming, SEO/SEM, PHP, HTML, Facebook, MS Office, Adobe Photoshop or Illustrator, GIMP, Adwords, Retargeting, Premiere, Dreamweaver, Google Analytics), language skills, written and verbal communication skills, project management, a driving license is needed - organised, independent, results-oriented, stress-resistant, dynamic, business-minded, energetic, detail-oriented, proactive, team work, interest in company activities and sector, problem-solving

Similar vacancies in Northern Europe	
Denmark	<i>Online marketingspecialist, Social Media Marketing Manager, Online marketingkonsulent, Web og marketingkoordinator</i>
Sweden	<i>Online Marketing Coordinator Global Media, Online marketing manager, Juniorkonsult Digital Markadsföring, Digital Marketing Specialist</i>
Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as the vacancies for Belgium? YES	<p>Tasks/Responsibilities: development and implementation of online marketing strategy, email marketing, branding, report preparation, data analysis, management and optimisation of campaigns, budget planning, set up a digital marketing toolbox, launch new campaigns via social media, monitoring, measurement and analysis of marketing plans</p> <p>Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tertiary education in a related field (bachelor's, master's), experience in a related position, field or company - knowledge of online marketing, market analysis, web experience, experience with SEO, InDesign, Illustrator, Adobe Photoshop, Salesforce, Hubspot, Google Adwords, DoubleClick, social media (Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube), a good understanding of online marketing and the web, web design skills, language skills, written and verbal communication skills - committed, passionate, creativity, independent, responsible, team-working skills, interested, proactive, ambitious, well-organised, adaptable, analytical mindset

Similar vacancies in Central and Eastern Europe	
Czech Republic	<i>E-Commerce Marketing Manager, Online Marketing Expert, Online marketing specialist, Online marketing manager</i>
Hungary	<i>Online Marketing munkatárs, Értékesítési/Marketing asszisztens, Online marketing specialist, Online marketing manager, Online marketing és kommunikációs specialist</i>
Poland	<i>Online Marketing Manager, Specjalista ds. marketingu online, E-Commerce Marketing Manager - branża sportowa</i>
Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as the vacancies for Belgium? YES	<p>Tasks/Responsibilities: preparation and implementation of online marketing campaigns or strategies, market research, copywriting, email marketing, drawing traffic to website, overseeing social media strategy, keeping track of emerging technologies, set up web, mobile or digital campaigns, measure and report performance of strategies, newsletter, content creation, branding, web design, search engine marketing</p> <p>Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high school education, vocational training, graduate professional degree, university degree, experience in similar role, firm, sector - knowledge of digital marketing, reporting, copywriting skills, MS Office, SEO/SEM, internet analytics and tools (Google Adwords, Display Ads, Mixpanel, Colibri, Crazy Egg, Brand24, Facebook-Ads), Photoshop, PPC, language skills, written and verbal communication skills, graphic skills, data analysis and reporting skills, market knowledge - customer-oriented, creative, loyal, independent, proactive, team player, positive, self-motivated, passion for marketing, flexibility

B. A global perspective

Results from [job portals](#) and [Google search](#) for countries in different parts of the world: we focus mainly on the United States, for which we find vacancies for *Online Marketing Specialist, Online Marketing Consultant, Integrated Digital Marketing Manager, Web Marketing Manager*.

Some of the job portals consulted: Indeed, Monster, Stepstone, ...

Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as the vacancies for Belgium? YES

- Tasks/Responsibilities are relatively similar to those for Belgium. Again, tasks commonly involve marketing (e.g. e-commerce, implementation of campaigns and strategies, promotions, content creation

for websites, social media, email marketing, paid advertising, branding, budget planning), sales and communications. In addition, some vacancies also refer to web design, copywriting and editing, as was the case for Belgium. Other tasks involve data analysis and database management, reporting on performance indicators, search for new technologies to use in daily tasks, continuous training and participation in workshops, conferences and industry events. These tasks seem to appear less in the Belgian vacancies (either not needed for position or assumed implicitly).

- Requirements are rather similar as well. Almost all vacancies require experience in a similar role and sector. Education and cognitive skills: at least a bachelor's degree in a related field, knowledge of online marketing techniques and strategies, web technology, organic search, search engine spiders and ranking factors, web design, MS Office, Google Analytics, HTML, CSS, written and communication skills, project management. Non-cognitive skills: teamwork, leadership skills, creativity, goal-oriented, positive, stress-resistant, problem-solving skills, self-motivated, able to do many tasks at once. Rather similar requirements, again a strong emphasis on the non-cognitive skills. We did find some differences in terms of the platforms and tools that are used, e.g. Google Adwords, SEOMoz, CrazyEg, Movable Ink, HubSpot.

C. A Google Trends Analysis

An analysis on the basis of Google Trends reveals the following patterns (see graphs, global): especially 'digital marketing' is on the rise, Internet marketing has declined over time and online marketing has been popular during the last five years (with a peak in 2013). These findings indicate that the Internet has become so widespread that the term and concept are relatively common nowadays. Nevertheless, the interest in occupations related to web-based marketing appears to grow. These patterns are found in Belgium, many European countries (France, Germany, the Netherlands, the UK, Italy, Finland, Sweden, Hungary, and Poland, among others) and the United States. Some differences are detected for online marketing (after the peak in 2013, the interest appears to remain somewhat higher in Denmark and Romania, and there is a slight upward trend for Spain) and internet marketing (high peaks and then a drop to nearly zero for Poland and Sweden).

Google Trends: online marketing worldwide (30/09/2015)

Google Trends: internet marketing worldwide (30/09/2015)

Google Trends: digital marketing worldwide (30/09/2015)

5.2.1.5 Occupational classification

A. International classifications

ISCO-08: the term 'online' does not appear in combination with 'marketing'; nor do 'digital' and 'internet'; the term 'internet' does appear in combination with 'salesperson' (occupation 5244: service & sales workers => sales workers => other sales workers => contact centre sales persons).

Where could this occupation fit in the ISCO08 classification?

- 1221 'Sales and marketing managers'.
- 1222 'Advertising and public relations managers'.
- 2431 'Advertising and marketing professionals'.

ESCO: it does not appear to exist at this point ('marketing' does exist)

Where could this occupation fit in the ESCO classification?

- 579 'Advertising and marketing professionals'.
- 563 'Sales, marketing and development managers'.
- 361 'Other sales workers'.

B. National classifications

Belgium: based on ISCO (from 2011 onwards).

In Europe:

- *France*: PCS and PCS-ESE, but occupation is not included there (different translations were checked; it might be due to the fact that the last update was in 2003).
- *Germany*: Klassifikation der Berufe (KB) (most recent version is 2010), occupation is included: 92113 Komplexe Spezialistentätigkeiten (includes *Online-Marketingmanager/in*) as part of the category *Werbung, Marketing, kaufmännische und redaktionelle Medienberufe*.
- *The Netherlands*: based on ISCO (Central Bureau for Statistics, from 2013 onwards).
- *UK*: SOC (most recent version is 2010), but occupation is not included there.
- *Italy*: has the Classificazione delle professioni (CP, most recent version 2011, an update of CP2001 and adapted to ISCO08), in this classification there is an occupation named *tecnici del marketing* (code 3.3.3.5.0, in which an example job title is *tecnico del web marketing*), that is part of the professioni tecniche nell'organizzazione, amministrazione e nelle attività finanziarie e commerciali/tecnici dei rapporti con i mercati/tecnici del marketing.
- *Spain*: has the Clasificación Nacional de Ocupaciones 2011 (CNO-11), includes marketing professionals (Profesionales de la publicidad y la comercialización) but it is not clear whether this covers online marketing professionals.
- *Denmark*: DISCO, Danish national classification based on ISCO, most recent version is DISCO 2008, not found.
- *Sweden*: has the Standard för svensk yrkesklassificering (SSYK) (most recent version is SSYK2012), based on ISCO08. Includes many marketing professions, but it does not seem to include online or web marketing.
- *Czech Republic*: Klasifikace zaměstnání (CZ-ISCO), based on ISCO08. Few marketing occupations, few web-related professions (not found in the list).
- *Hungary*: has HCSO/FEOR (edition 2008), but this does not include the occupation.
- *Poland*: has the Klasyfikacja zawodów i specjalności (KZiS 2014), based on ISCO08 (but it is updated more recently, 2014). In an alphabetical list, a similar occupation was found: 122104 *Kierownik do spraw marketingu internetowego* (Director of Marketing online). This is likely the result of the recent update.

In the rest of the world (US):

- *US* has SOC (last version is 2010), occupation is included: 11-2021 Marketing Managers lists 'Internet Marketing Managers' as an example job title (part of 11-2000 Advertising, Marketing, Promotions, Public Relations, and Sales Managers).
- *US* also has the *O*NET* classification: the occupation exists as part of 'Online Merchants' (13-1199.06 – Online Merchants www.onetonline.org/link/summary/13-1199.06). This occupation is labelled as a '*Bright Outlook*' occupation (in the category 'new and emerging'), i.e. occupations expected to grow rapidly in the next several years, will have large numbers of job openings, or are new and emerging occupations.

O*NET summary of online merchants: Conduct retail activities of businesses operating exclusively online; may perform duties such as preparing business strategies, buying merchandise, managing inventory, implementing marketing activities, fulfilling and shipping online orders, and balancing financial records.

Examples of job titles: Marketing Director; Marketing Specialist; Online Marketing Manager; Online Services Manager; Social Media Director.

Other O*NET occupations that are related to ‘Online marketing’:

- Search Marketing Strategists: www.onetonline.org/link/summary/15-1199.10
- Marketing Managers: www.onetonline.org/link/summary/11-2021.00
- Market Research Analysts and Marketing Specialists: www.onetonline.org/link/summary/13-1161.00

5.2.1.6 Conclusions

Is Online Marketing Coordinator a new or emerging occupation?	
In Belgium?	<p>Given its limited prevalence and the relative novelty of some of the tools and technologies that the worker has to use, the occupation is <u>relatively new and emerging</u> in Belgium. The tasks and duties that are involved in the job are highly specialised, but there still is a clear link with other existing jobs (among others, in marketing, sales, communication). The occupation seems to combine different aspects of these jobs (marketing, social media, IT). Its importance is likely to grow in the future, as the Internet is increasingly used in everyday life. In some industries and firms, the occupation is likely to be completely new, while in other industries and companies, it is emerging. Interestingly, one of the vacancies mentioned that the position is new within the organisation. Does this occupation <u>have a future</u>? Undoubtedly yes.</p> <p>What is the <u>impact on training</u>? What are the <u>skills implications</u>? Educational institutes will have to keep in mind that the marketing professions of the future will also have a strong web-based dimension. This means that students will need to learn how to work with these programs, tools and platforms (Google Analytics, SEO, email marketing, social media) and how to reach their target audience in this way. They also have to acquire some programming skills, web and graphic design skills, etc. Marketing jobs are likely to develop into broader professions, and students will thus have to develop a wider range of skills as well. Another important dimension that should not be overlooked is data and analytics. Strong analytical skills are essential (data collection, result interpretation, reporting, drawing conclusions to adjust strategies and develop new campaigns). Finally, training programmes should focus extensively on communication skills, because these are requested in nearly all vacancies. Moreover, firms that want to remain competitive should make sure that their employees receive on-the-job training or have other training opportunities, to keep up with technological changes and changes in the market. Similarly, for the workers that hold a marketing position, it could be interesting to engage in life-long-learning and to keep up to date with current developments (to keep their job or transfer to other positions).</p>
In Europe?	<p>A similar conclusion is reached for Europe. In many countries, the classification is not present in the most recent national occupational classification. In some countries, i.e. Germany, Italy and Poland, the occupation is part of the most recent national occupational classification (there it could be regarded as emerging rather than new). There are a lot of vacancies for similar positions across Europe, especially in the west, north and south, less so in the east.</p> <p>Given that the tasks and responsibilities and the requirements are comparable in other European countries, the conclusions formulated above apply here. Education should focus on new technologies, communication skills and data analysis. Companies can benefit from providing on-the-job training to their staff, to keep up with recent developments. Marketing professionals should be aware of these developments and engage in training activities too.</p>
Worldwide?	<p>For the US, the occupation appears to be relatively new or emerging as well, depending on the industry and firm. The occupation is included in SOC and O*NET. Similar conclusions are reached for the educational institutes, firms and individuals.</p>

5.3 Second example of an occupation card: ‘Drug Safety Specialist’

5.3.1 Occupation Card 2: Drug Safety Specialist

Date: 3 November 2015.

5.3.1.1 Identification

The identification of new occupations, such as the drug safety specialist presented in the current document, is based on an innovative methodology that we are piloting here. This methodology is embedded in the rapidly growing strand of the literature that relies on web-based data sources to conduct labour market research (see Askitas & Zimmermann, 2015). The main idea behind our methodology is to identify new occupations via the *occupational classification* that online job portals use to guide job seekers on their website. Typically, such occupational classifications have - at their core - a *tag system*, i.e. a list of tags that is used to assign vacancies to specific job categories. This list of tags can be published online or stored in a library accessed by an API search when a job seeker enters a word in the search box. Earlier research suggests that job portals tend to regularly update their list of tags, to account for the emergence of new occupations and the disappearance of redundant ones.

In our pilot study, we focus on 11 countries for which we keep track of one of their main online job portals. For these countries, we created a *benchmark*, which is composed of their occupational classification (their list of tags) on 30 June 2015. Our goal is to determine whether this tag system could also be used to identify new occupations, by comparing the benchmark classification with the *current occupational classification* of the portal at regularly intervals, i.e. every month. The *tags that are not yet included* in the benchmark, i.e. missing from the list of tags when the benchmark and the new list of tags are compared, could point to new or emerging occupations. For more details on our methodology, we refer to the *Methodological Note* that is available on the website in the New Occupations Observatory.

In July 2015, a new tag was added to the *Slovakian* online job board in our pilot. This tag was picked up (either via the API or via a web crawling technique that extracts the list of tags - this depends on the portal) and stored in a database. We then searched for an actual vacancy for a *drug safety specialist* on this portal (to discover what triggered the new tag). More details on this tag/vacancy can be found below; these details cover (i) the portal to which the tag was added and on which the vacancy was found, and (ii) the content of the sample vacancy that we study in more depth (to identify tasks and responsibilities – skills and other requirements).

Details on the tag and the job advertisement	
When did the tag/vacancy appear online?	October 2015
On which online job board was the tag/vacancy published?	profesia.sk
Which country is covered by this job portal?	Slovakia
In which industry is the employer active?	Pharmaceuticals
What type of employer has posted the vacancy?	Private company

We found overall three job vacancies on the Slovakian job portal under the searched category of drug safety specialist. Only one of these jobs consisted only of this one category (Safety Manager); the other two consisted of more categories (Quality Manager/Responsible Pharma and Pharmacist). Consequently, we will be primarily referring to the found job vacancy of ‘Safety Manager’ when talking about drug safety specialist since this specific vacancy was the most narrowly defined in terms of chosen categories. Further in the text we will provide more specific elaboration on similarity of the other two mentioned vacancies with the occupation of drug safety specialist.

Sample job advertisement	
Job description (responsibilities and tasks of the job)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complex responsibility for managing safety-related activities based on the legislative requirements within the local affiliate - Representing the local safety function on behalf of the country in interactions with regulatory agencies and senior management - Ensuring local compliance with pharmacovigilance requirements in accordance with local regulations and procedures - Active monitoring local/regional operating performance and adverse events reporting - Maintain up-to-date knowledge and compliance with local safety regulations for country - Ensuring the training of local staff regarding the adverse reporting obligations - Ensuring that local processes, strategies and initiatives are aligned with safety defined by the company - Intensive contact with International Safety group - Acting as a contact person for regional safety inspections and audits - Reporting to Regional Safety Lead
Job profile (education, skills and other requirements for the job)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least a bachelor's degree in pharmacology or life science - Fluent English - Minimum five years of previous related experience with safety and pharmacovigilance processes - Deep understanding of local pharmacovigilance requirements and practices - Ability to work with significant autonomy - Ability to understand and communicate scientific information - Ability to build strong business relationships - Demonstrated problem-solving abilities - Excellent organisational and communication skills
Job portal tags (tags attached to the vacancy on the job board)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safety Manager tags: Drug Safety Specialist - Quality Manager tags: Drug Safety Specialist, Pharmacist, Regulatory Affairs Manager, Regulatory Affairs Specialist - Pharmacist: Drug Safety Specialist, Clinical Data Manager, Pharmacist, Pharmaceutical Laboratorian, Medical Advisor

5.3.1.2 Definition, responsibilities and tasks

A. Definition

What is 'Drug Safety Specialist'?

Drug Safety Specialist is mainly concerned with pharmacovigilance. According to the World Health Organization, pharmacovigilance comprises activities related to 'detection, assessment, understanding and prevention of adverse effects or any other drug-related problem'. It is possible to perform this occupation at the clinical level which involves primarily scientific activities in drug research and, secondly, on the administrative level where an individual supervises accordance of processes with internal and external regulations. Needless to say, it is common to find the interconnection of these two aspects, especially abroad. However, in case of Slovakia we have not found the clinical aspects of this occupation in the job vacancies such as scientific involvement in clinical trials. As a result, the majority of the workload of the drug safety specialist in Slovakia consists of communicating with and reporting to state regulatory agencies. Moreover, the drug safety specialist might also operate as an *auditor* for supervising internal regulations on behalf of company management or an international institution.

Examples of job titles:

- *abroad*: Drug Safety Specialist, Clinical Drug Safety Specialist, Product Safety Specialist;
- *in Slovakia*: Safety Manager, Quality Manager/Responsible Pharma.

More information about the specifics of drug safety specialist occupation, i.e. pharmacovigilance may be found on:

- *Wikipedia*: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pharmacovigilance>
- *World Health Organization*:
www.who.int/medicines/areas/quality_safety/safety_efficacy/pharmvigi/en/

Is this position related to any existing occupations?

Drug safety specialist combines responsibilities of other similar occupations. It is especially related to *regulatory affairs occupations* and *compliance occupations*, such as regulatory affairs manager, regulatory affairs specialist, corporate regulatory affairs specialist, regulatory affairs officer, compliance officer, compliance specialist, etc. The duties of the regulatory affairs and compliance occupations are specified as analysing local regulations, supervising and ensuring that company's processes are in compliance with local and international law. However, drug safety specialist is closely concerned with the pharmaceutical sector in comparison with other compliance and regulatory affairs occupations which do not have to be necessarily concerned solely with pharmaceuticals. Furthermore, the clear distinction between regulatory affairs/ compliance specialist and drug safety specialist in the pharmaceutical industry seems to be the drug safety specialist's specifically defined interest with processes concerned with pharmacovigilance regulations only.

How prevalent is the occupation of a Drug Safety Specialist in Slovakia?

We looked for similar occupations on several job portals and did a Google search. Results of this exercise:

Job portals

- profesia.sk: three vacancies for the entry 'Drug safety specialist'.
- inzerciapraca.sk: zero vacancies for the entry 'Drug safety specialist'.
- kariera.zoznam.sk: zero vacancies for the entry 'Drug safety specialist'.
- inzeraty.sme.sk: zero vacancies for the entry 'Drug safety specialist'.
- praca.bazos.sk: zero vacancies for the entry 'Drug safety specialist'.
- ponuky.sk: zero vacancies for the entry 'Drug safety specialist'.

Google Search (limited to .sk websites)

- drug safety specialist: about 4,700 results.
- 'drug safety specialist': about 2,600 results.
- compliance specialist: about 3,800 results.
- pharmaceutical compliance specialist: about 4,600 results.
- regulatory affairs: about 10,000 results.
- regulatory affairs specialist: about 4,500 results.
- pharmaceutical regulatory affairs: about 12,000 results.

B. What are the responsibilities and tasks of a drug safety specialist?

This information is obtained from a sample of job vacancies, extracted from job portals (for Slovakia).

As was mentioned before, the search mechanism on Slovak job portal profesia.sk is based on tags – categories which we also used. Using the tag 'drug safety specialist', we found three vacancies. Only one of these vacancies, 'safety manager', was solely concerned with pharmacovigilance and consisted

of only one category, which was searched. The other two vacancies consisted of more categories and were minimally concerned with pharmacovigilance.

- First, the job advertisement for ‘pharmacist’ was not concerned with pharmacovigilance at all; moreover, this job could be identified as a standard drug dispenser job in public pharmacy. It seems that the advertiser inserted the tag ‘drug safety specialist’ mistakenly into the advertisement.
- Second, the job advertisement for ‘Quality manager/Responsible pharma’ included ‘drug safety specialist’, too; however, we found no pharmacovigilance aspect in the tasks and responsibilities. The only part of the advertisement explicitly mentioning pharmacovigilance was the requirements section, where the applicants were required to have regulatory/drug safety experience. Other than that, this job vacancy can be identified as a vacancy for a head drug dispenser with management responsibilities.

As a consequence, in the following sections we will be working with the advertisement for ‘safety manager’, since this ad was almost exclusively concerned with pharmacovigilance, regulatory and compliance tasks.

- In general, tasks and responsibilities are closely related to those of *regulatory affairs* and *compliance occupations*. They include maintaining compliance with local drug safety regulations and regular filing of reports to local regulators.
- Ensuring that processes are aligned with internal regulations. At the same time serving as a contact person for inspections and audits. Consequently, we can see aspects of the *auditor’s occupation*.
- The tasks also include intensive cooperation with international safe regulation bodies, such as International Safety Group.
- We also notice the requirement of *training/coaching* skills, which are required to provide trainings for local staff with regard to the adverse reporting obligations.

5.3.1.3 Education, skills and other requirements

This information is obtained from a sample of vacancies, extracted from job portals (for Slovakia).

Formal education required	
Is formal education required?	Yes
Level of education	Tertiary education: bachelor’s degree
Field of education	Pharmaceutical education

Skills required	
Communication skills	Excellent communication skills, fluent English in written and spoken form
Computer skills	Not required/not specified (in Slovakia)
Non-cognitive skills	Ability to work with significant autonomy, ability to understand and communicate scientific information, ability to build strong business relationships, demonstrated problem-solving abilities, excellent organisational skills
Occupation-specific skills	Deep understanding of local pharmacovigilance requirements and practice

Experience required	
Is experience required?	Minimum two to five years of previous related experience with safety and pharmacovigilance processes
Is job-related experience required?	Yes, previous experience in the sector, experience in communication with local regulators

5.3.1.4 Geographical prevalence

A. A European perspective

Results from [job portals](#) and [Google search](#) for countries in different parts of Europe:

In case job descriptions (tasks, requirements) differ significantly in the predefined clusters of countries, we will present them separately.

Similar vacancies in Western Europe	
France	<i>Pharmacien(ne) assurance qualité, Responsable assurance qualité, Pharmacien responsable assurance qualité, Responsable de l'assurance qualité</i>
Germany	<i>Apotheker als stellv. Leiter Qualitätskontrolle, Global Quality Auditor, Manager Drug Safety – Pharmacovigilance, Medical Manager Drug Safety, Drug Safety Manager</i>
The Netherlands	<i>Drug Safety Manager, Regulatory affairs officer, Drug Safety and Quality Officer, Pharmacovigilance Liaison Manager</i>
UK	<i>Drug Safety Associate, Drug Safety Manager, Drug Safety Officer, Drug Safety Specialist, Drug Safety Physician</i>
Belgium	<i>Regulatory Affairs Officer/Regulatory Affairs Specialist (with explicit aim at pharmacovigilance and safety, pharmaceutical development and quality, and other regulatory affairs and operations)</i>
Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as the vacancies for Slovakia? YES	<p>Tasks/Responsibilities: ensuring that products and processes comply with national and international regulations, preparing documentation for regulatory bodies, managing and participating in the implementation of the quality system, conducting quality audits, managing quality trainings and staff qualifications</p> <p>Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scientific or medical university degree - in most of the cases experience in the related field is required (could be substituted by a PhD degree in one case) - knowledge of national and international regulations

Similar vacancies in Southern Europe	
Italy	<i>Medico Farmacovigilanza, Drug safety officer, Addetto alla farmacovigilanza, Drug Safety Specialist, Drug Safety Physician</i>
Spain	<i>Responsable de Calidad Sector Químico, Especialista en Farmacovigilancia</i>
Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as the vacancies for Slovakia? YES	<p>Tasks/Responsibilities: identification of adverse effects, following national and international regulations, communication and collaboration with regulators, providing pharmacovigilance reports resulting from clinical trials, providing pharmacovigilance trainings for the staff, ensuring the maintenance of product quality and quality system</p> <p>Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - degree in medicine, biology, pharmacy, biotechnology or other life science - experience in pharmacovigilance (some jobs had this requirement preferred but not required) - knowledge of current legislation

Similar vacancies in Northern Europe	
Denmark	<i>Pharmacovigilance Policy Expert</i>
Sweden	<i>Regulatory Affairs Konsulter</i>
Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as the vacancies for Slovakia? PARTLY	<p>Tasks/Responsibilities:</p> <p>DK: reviewing new global pharmacovigilance regulatory guidelines, performing the impact assessment on global safety procedures, writing reports for external regulators and relevant internal departments</p> <p>SWE: to serve as a contact person for regulation affairs with authorities</p> <p>Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - master's degree in pharmacy or other relevant life science - previous experience in the pharmaceutical sector

Similar vacancies in Central and Eastern Europe	
Czech Republic	<i>Drug Safety Associate</i>
Hungary	<i>Gyógyszerbiztonsági munkatárs - Adatmenedzsment területre (Drug Safety Associate - Data Management area, Minőségbiztosítási auditor -Gyógyszeripar (Quality Assurance Auditor – Pharmaceuticals), Gyógyszerbiztonsági Koordinátor (Pharmaceutical Product Safety Coordinator)</i>
Poland	<i>None found</i>
Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as the vacancies for Slovakia? PARTLY	<p><u>Tasks/Responsibilities:</u></p> <p>CZ: development project specific reporting procedures, workflows and templates; support project specific safety database set-up, development of data entry guidelines, and user acceptance testing; electronic documentation and quality control of drug safety information; coding of data in the safety database and writing case narratives</p> <p>HU: drug safety data processing, keep track of current regulatory and corporate standards in pharmacovigilance, participation in drug safety audits and inspections, IT support for drug safety database; determination of the completeness of single case reports, confirmation of the accuracy of medical coding</p> <p><u>Requirements:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - degree in pharmacy, nursing, life science or other health-related field - appropriate previous experience - ability to interpret and apply global safety regulations - IT skills – database management, MS Office (partly in Hungary)

B. A global perspective

Results from [job portals](#) and [Google search](#) for countries in different parts of the world: we focus mainly on the United States, for which we find vacancies for *Drug Safety Specialist*, *Clinical Drug Safety Specialist*, *Safety and Pharmacovigilance Specialist*, *Drug Safety Associate* and *Senior Drug Safety Specialist*.

Do these vacancies involve **similar tasks** and have *similar requirements* as the vacancies for Slovakia? *PARTLY*

- Tasks/Responsibilities are relatively similar to those for Slovakia when it comes to interaction with regulators. Processes related to drug safety not only have to be in compliance with national and international regulation standards but also with internal standards. Duties and responsibilities also include training of staff, reviewing and filing drug safety reports. These tasks are congruent with the tasks described in Slovakian ads. On the other side, Slovakian ads do not explicitly mention clinical trial involvement. Especially in the US ads, clinical drug safety specialists are required to provide clinical trial support and actively cooperate on the methodology, coding and inspection of the products even in the clinical trial testing. The main difference between clinical drug safety specialist and drug safety specialist is that the drug safety specialist's work is mainly based on reports and data provided by clinical trials team while the clinical drug safety specialist is actively involved in the development of the drug during the clinical trials.
- Requirements are rather similar to Slovakian advertisements. Pharmaceutical, medical or other life science education is required. Almost all vacancies require experience in a similar role and sector. The usual length of required experience in the related field is two to five years. Furthermore, excellent knowledge of local, national and international regulations is necessary. Non-cognitive skills required around the world are often: analytical thinking, organisational skills, ability to work both independently and in a team, and strong ability to work with scientific information. Moreover, excellent communication skills are required, as well as fluent English with understanding of medical/pharmaceutical/scientific terminology.

C. A Google Trends Analysis

An analysis on the basis of Google Trends reveals the following patterns (see graphs, global):

we can notice that pharmacovigilance, i.e. drug safety, fluctuates around the stable values. Even though a sudden rise in pharmacovigilance in recent years is not apparent, it can be deduced from the graph Google Trends 2 that the term ‘pharmacovigilance jobs’ has been constantly on the rise since 2009. Before this year, there was almost no interest in pharmacovigilance jobs in via Internet browsing. Furthermore, when looking at the graph Google Trends 3, we can see brief, sharp rises in 2014 and 2015 in the worldwide Internet search for the job ‘Drug Safety Specialist’. As a result, we can assume that this occupation has recently emerged as part of the recent, gradual rise of the pharmacovigilance sector.

Google Trends 1: ‘Pharmacovigilance’ worldwide (30/10/2015)

Google Trends 2: ‘Pharmacovigilance jobs’ worldwide (30/10/2015)

Google Trends 3: 'Drug Safety Specialist' worldwide (30/10/2015)

5.3.1.5 Occupational classification

A. International classifications

ISCO-08: as was mentioned in the Google Trends Analysis above, pharmacovigilance jobs started emerging in 2009; furthermore, specifically 'drug safety specialist' started to show up only in 2014. As a result, there is not any separate category for these occupations created in the ISCO classification from 2008. Consequently, we determined which categories at least partly cover the aspects of the drug safety specialist occupation.

Where could this occupation fit in the ISCO08 classification?

- 3141 'Life Science Technicians (excluding Medical)' – this category is especially suitable for more clinically oriented pharmacovigilance jobs, as Life Science Technicians are primarily concerned with aspects of research.
- 2262 'Pharmacists' - this category only partially covers pharmacovigilance occupations since pharmacovigilance jobs are not involved in drug dispensing. On the other side, pharmacists are in this category's definition also concerned drug safety and drug standards.

ESCO: it does not appear to exist separately in the ESCO classification.

Where could this occupation fit in the ESCO classification?

- 'Drug Inspector' - according to ESCO, this classification also has the 2262 ISCO code, which is 'pharmacist'. Additionally, skills and competences described in ESCO are related to a drug safety specialist's tasks and responsibilities. For instance, supervision of medical products, clinical testing and, partly, laboratory analysis.

B. National classifications

Slovakia: the national classification in Slovakia is based on ISCO08 and is fully compatible with it.

In Europe:

- *France*: PCS and PCS-ESE, however, occupation is not included there (the last update of this national occupational classification was in 2003);
- *Germany*: Klassifikation der Berufe (KB) (most recent version is 2010), occupation is not included;
- *Belgium*: based on ISCO (from 2011 onwards);
- *The Netherlands*: based on ISCO (Central Bureau for Statistics, from 2013 onwards);

- *UK*: SOC (most recent version is 2010), drug safety specialist could be included in the category 2642 Quality assurance and Regulatory professionals where these occupations are listed: Compliance manager, Quality assurance manager, Quality manager;
- *Italy*: has the *Classificazione delle professioni* (CP, most recent version 2011, an update of CP2001 and adapted to ISCO-08), however, there is no relevant category for drug safety specialist;
- *Spain*: has the *Clasificación Nacional de Ocupaciones 2011* (CNO-11). The closest classification that suits drug safety specialist is category 3204 Chemical and Pharmaceutical Supervisors. However, this category is sorted under 320 Mining, manufacturing and construction supervisors and since the categories in Spanish occupational classification are not defined more specifically we cannot certainly determine whether the mentioned category is suitable for drug safety specialist;
- *Denmark*: DISCO, Danish national classification based on ISCO, most recent version is DISCO 2008. We have not found any appropriate category for drug safety specialist;
- *Sweden*: has the *Standard för svensk yrkesklassificering* (SSYK) (most recent version is SSYK2012), based on ISCO08. It does not seem to include the drug safety specialist occupation or similar category;
- *Czech Republic*: *Klasifikace zaměstnání* (CZ-ISCO), based on ISCO08. No relevant category for drug safety specialist was found;
- *Hungary*: has HCSO/FEOR (edition 2008). The specific occupations are not closely described, but judging from the occupation names, 3135 Quality assurance technician could include some of the working aspects of drug safety specialist;
- *Poland*: has the *Klasyfikacja zawodów i specjalności* (KZiS 2014), based on ISCO-08 (but it was updated more recently, 2014). In an alphabetical list, a similar occupation was found: 242208 *Inspektor farmaceutyczny* (Pharmaceutical Inspector). This occupation most likely involves some aspects of the drug safety specialist occupation such as supervising drug safety standards.

In the rest of the world (US):

- *US* has SOC (last version is 2010), however, drug safety is not specifically defined in this classification. Other similar occupation in the US SOC is 13-1040/1 *Compliance officer*;
- *US* also has the *O*NET* classification where the specifically named occupation ‘drug safety specialist/manager/etc’ cannot be found; however, the agenda of this occupation can be found in the category 13-1041.07 *Regulatory Affairs Specialists* which includes occupations such as *Drug Regulatory Affairs Specialist*, *Quality Assurance/Regulatory Affairs Specialist*. These occupations fulfil the definition of drug safety specialist to a great extent. Moreover, this occupation is also labelled a ‘*Bright Outlook*’ occupation (in the category ‘new and emerging’), i.e. occupations expected to grow rapidly in the next several years, will have large numbers of job openings, or are new and emerging occupations; *O*NET* summary of regulatory affairs specialists: Coordinate and document internal regulatory processes, such as internal audits, inspections, license renewals, or registrations. May compile and prepare materials for submission to regulatory agencies.

5.3.1.6 F. Conclusions

Is Drug Safety Specialist a new or emerging occupation?	
In Slovakia?	<p>We assess that the occupation drug safety specialist is relatively <u>new and emerging</u> in Slovakia. Even though similar occupations have existed since a long time in Slovakia, new pharmacovigilance jobs like drug safety specialist merged tasks and responsibilities from them and narrowed them to a specific objective, which is its dedication to drug safety legislation. Similar occupations are regulatory affairs and compliance jobs aimed at the pharmaceutical sector. Nevertheless, as has been mentioned, the added value of drug safety specialist for the job market in Slovakia is its very narrow specialisation in pharmacovigilance. Moreover, it can be assumed that this sector has extensive growth potential. More specifically, we found only one current advertisement which was exclusively dedicated to drug safety; however, it lacked a clinical aspect, i.e. active involvement in research – clinical trials. As will be described below, in comparison with Slovakia, drug safety occupations abroad are also focused on the active role of the individual and his supervision of the pharmaceutical research and development, whilst in Slovakia the current advertisement is almost solely focused on communication with regulators, maintaining compliance with drug safety regulations and staff training. As a consequence, <u>it can be expected that more pharmacovigilance will start emerging in Slovakia</u> with active involvement in clinical trials because the current requirements for pharmacovigilance jobs in Slovakia demand only understanding scientific information from clinical trials and further working with it.</p> <p>What is the <u>impact on training</u>? What are the <u>skills implications</u>?</p> <p>First of all, promising candidates for pharmacovigilance jobs have to have excellent English language skills, especially regarding pharmaceutical terminology, since all the major employers are supranational pharmaceutical corporations. Additionally, while knowledge of national regulations is required, flawless knowledge of international regulations is requested. Secondly, cross-sectional skills from pharmaceuticals, law, computer, database, and statistics are starting to be demanded abroad; as a result, we can anticipate the same trend in Slovakia. As for now, pharmaceutical or other life sciences education is required with quite extensive previous field experience which we assume ensures knowledge of relevant regulatory legislation. Statistical and database skills should also be developed, as we can notice from the abroad experience that one of the tasks of pharmacovigilance occupations might be data processing. One of the solutions for this growing job market seems to be introduction of new study programmes aimed directly and solely at pharmacovigilance, which we already noticed in other countries.</p> <p>For instance: www.postgraduatesearch.com/university-of-hertfordshire/52981048/postgraduate-course.htm.</p>
In Europe?	<p>Similar conclusions can be drawn in Southern, Central, Northern, Eastern, and, in part, Western Europe as those in Slovakia. However, we found no separate occupational classification in national classifications for pharmacovigilance jobs across the studied European countries. On the other side, we can still consider drug safety occupations as new and emerging and see them showing up in a lot of variations in terms of specialisation, e.g. data management, regulatory affairs, research and development involvement, or a combination thereof. In terms of Europe, most job advertisements for drug safety occupations were in Western Europe. For instance, we found no job offer for drug safety/pharmacovigilance specialists in Poland. Requirements and tasks are similar to those in the Slovakian ad, though we notice explicit mentions of clinical trial involvement and clinical data-processing and management (Hungary and, in part, Czech Republic). On the other hand, the overwhelming majority of tasks and responsibilities across Europe was still dedicated to regulatory affairs and compliance maintenance with external regulations.</p>
Worldwide?	<p>In comparison with all the other studied countries, pharmacovigilance jobs seem to be most on the rise in the US. We found a large number of US advertisements for various forms of pharmacovigilance jobs. We could clearly distinguish orientation, whether toward regulatory affairs or research and development, e.g. clinical trials. Either variations, or a combination thereof require pharmaceutical education, but in the case of regulatory affairs the stress is placed on pharmaceutical regulation knowledge while clinical drug safety specialists require a more extensive scientific background. Moreover, the US is the only studied country that included in its national occupational classification, O*NET, <i>Regulatory affairs specialist</i>, which includes <i>Drug Regulatory Affairs Specialist</i>, <i>Quality Assurance/Regulatory Affairs Specialist</i>.</p>

5.4 Summary

- With this pilot, our aim was to test whether it is feasible to identify potentially new or emerging occupations on the basis of the *occupational structure or the meta data available on online job portals*.
- The pilot confirms that this methodology is effective and easy to carry out. The output of the exercise is presented in a series of occupation cards. Each card provides detailed information on the potentially new occupation, in terms of their responsibilities and tasks, requirements, prevalence etc.
- When the benchmark was first established, we noted substantial heterogeneity in terms of the number of tags it contained for each country. Similarly, when the number of new tags is compared, there are many cross-country differences. Yet, these numbers are not easy to compare and may reflect differences in how the portals operate. We detected 57 potentially new occupations over a six-month period, for 6 countries.
- To the best of our knowledge, we are not aware of other research that uses a similar approach to identify new and emerging occupations. Traditionally, the identification is based on trade publications, employer surveys, job postings, interviews, surveys and existing occupational classifications.
- Further improvements of the methodology could involve extracting the list of tags on a quarterly rather than a monthly basis, which seems to be too frequent. Other possibilities are to carry out the work for a longer period, as we only ran the pilot for about six months, use more diverse data sources, automate some of the steps of the process and link the card to existing tools to identify new and emerging skills. This can be achieved by applying machine learning and text mining techniques (Grus, 2015).

6. Case Study 5: ‘The importance of foreign language skills in the labour markets of Central and Eastern Europe: an assessment based on data from online job portals’

(Beblavý et al., 2016b)

The fifth case study that we carried out in light of the InGRID project was also based on meta data extracted from online job portals. In contrast to the other case study in which we use such data, we do not combine them with vacancies in this case. Instead, our aim was to rely on the occupational classification and the ‘tag’ system that job boards use to organise their vacancies.³ We do, however, consider the number of vacancies associated with these tags in our analysis. The reason why we experiment with this system is that using tags and vacancy counts is much easier and faster than extracting a sample of job postings and doing a semantic analysis. At the same time, it brings less information. The aim of this case study was, therefore, to assess whether a simpler methodology could give interesting results.

In order to put this alternative methodology to the test, we investigate the demand for foreign language skills in the Visegrad region (which is composed of the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland and Slovakia). The Visegrad region (or V4) is a particularly interesting case, as it is well connected to the global economy and has strong historical, cultural and economic ties with its German speaking neighbours. Yet the region’s population only has a limited knowledge of foreign languages (according to the 2012 Eurobarometer).

6.1 Demand for foreign language skills for all occupations

We started our case study by *extracting the total number of vacancies* from each job portal (15,269 vacancies were available on the Czech job board, 11,231 on the Hungarian job board, 36,079 on the Polish job board and 11,344 on the Slovak job board, i.e. about 74,000 advertisements in total across the countries and considering all occupations). Then, we considered *how many of these carried tags refer to foreign language skills*.⁴

Many of the vacancies published on the job portals do not require any foreign language skills, i.e. they carry the ‘no foreign languages needed’ tag. More specifically, 38% of the vacancies of the Czech job board do not call for foreign language skills. This percentage is equal to 25% for Hungary and 43% for Slovakia. As no such tag is available on the Polish job board, we have no information on the share of vacancies that do not require any foreign language skills in this case (and we cannot calculate this number, as a single job advertisement may have multiple tags). In addition, we can only use advertisements that are explicitly tagged. Nevertheless, from these first results we can already conclude that there is substantial heterogeneity across the four countries when it comes to foreign language skills demand. In addition, the demand for such skills can be quite substantial.

³ One also has to keep in mind that the tags are not disjunctive groups: a single vacancy may carry multiple tags.

⁴ In practice, job seekers can indicate on the website that they are looking for a position where ‘English’ is a requirement, filtering out jobs for which this is not needed.

We then focus on the occupations that do carry foreign language tags. In Table 6.1, we report the share of vacancies that refer to foreign languages, including English, German, French, Spanish, Italian and Russian. When all vacancies are considered simultaneously, we find that 52% of them is tagged ‘English’, 12% is tagged ‘German’, 2% is tagged ‘French’, and less than 2% is tagged ‘Italian’, ‘Spanish’ or ‘Russian’. English clearly is the most requested foreign language while German comes in the second place. This pattern re-emerges if we focus on each of the countries separately. In all countries, English is the most-frequently-requested foreign language but there is considerable variation: whereas 28% of the Czech vacancies are tagged ‘English’, this number reaches 64% in Poland (for Hungary it is 39%, for Slovakia 49%). German is the second-most-demanded language in each of the countries, though the percentage of vacancies that carries this tag is much smaller than for English. Across the V4, the share ranges from 10% in the Czech Republic to 15% in Slovakia. Even though French, Italian and Spanish are used extensively in the EU, these three languages are hardly demanded in the Visegrad labour markets.

Table 6.1 Share of vacancies for each country and in total that list foreign language skills

	Czech Republic	Hungary	Poland	Slovakia	Total
English	28.19	38.92	63.99	49.26	51.89
German	10.15	10.86	12.45	14.59	12.36
French	0.65	1.25	3.56	1.50	2.33
Italian	0.19	0.67	1.65	0.55	1.05
Spanish	0.15	0.52	2.13	0.48	1.23
Russian	0.54	0.21	1.60	0.48	0.96
None	37.62	23.66	N/A	42.67	N/A

These percentages should be interpreted with some caution, as they might reflect seasonal dynamics (our data were collected in the month of July). To rule out seasonal dynamics, we contacted each of the job boards to inquire about the statistics for the entire year 2015. The Slovak job board informed us that 46% of the vacancies required English, while 14% required German. In the Czech Republic, the 10% share of advertisements for German was confirmed, but the share for English was reported to vary between 28% and 59% depending on whether the vacancies were supplied by public employment agencies or employers. The Hungarian portal reported that 55% the vacancies demanded English or German, 10% specifically requests English and 2% specifically call for German. We did not receive any further information from the Polish job board, unfortunately.

6.2 Demand for foreign language skills for a subset of occupations which could be identified in all four countries

As a next step, we reduce our sample and focus only on those occupations for which we can find at least 30 vacancies in each of the V4 countries. To this end, we had to map occupations from the different countries (i.e. to check which occupations match). This mapping resulted in a subsample of 59 occupations which could be identified in all four countries. For these occupations, we again derived the total number of available job advertisements and the share of these advertisements that refer to foreign language skills from the job boards.

The 59 occupations are listed in Table 6.2, which also presents the share of vacancies in each of the countries that require English language skills. Especially occupations with ISCO codes 2 and 4, the professional and administrative occupations, frequently demand English language skills. For occupations involving manual work, such skills seem to be less important. Another interesting result

is that particularly in Poland, some of the ISCO 7 occupations (craftsmen), show a relatively high demand for English language skills. This may indicate that these workers are employed by foreign employers or that they work abroad. Figure 6.1 summarises these results, by subdividing the occupations into three groups depending on whether the share of vacancies that call for English language skills is high or low.

Table 6.2 Share of vacancies that require English language skills across the Visegrad region. The occupations with the highest share are indicated in blue, the occupations with the lowest share in red

ISCO	Occupation	Czech Republic	Hungary	Poland	Slovakia
1135	HR Manager	87	42	67	67
1211	Financial Manager	63	54	62	50
1213	Operations Manager	53	48	65	59
1221	Marketing Manager	71	95	79	86
1221	Sales Director	53	45	49	51
1321	Production Director	69	50	55	74
2139	Consultant	44	64	49	66
2141	Industrial Engineer	86	81	85	83
2142	Civil Engineer	23	24	22	34
2149	Tester	88	87	76	89
2164	Architect	66	50	64	79
2211	Doctor	31	56	44	26
2221	Nurse	27	30	64	21
2330	Teacher	51	15	55	27
2411	Financial Controller	83	78	72	93
2411	Tax Advisor	81	50	86	98
2412	Financial Analyst	81	78	72	88
2431	Business Analyst	74	97	81	70
2431	Key Account Manager	63	90	45	71
2431	Marketing Professional	68	85	55	71
2433	Product Manager	83	94	74	74
2511	IT Analyst	81	87	74	88
2512	Programmer	82	84	77	85
2519	Computer Specialist	82	83	74	80
2519	Project Manager	81	68	75	84
2611	Lawyer	72	42	72	90
3112	Technician	56	35	34	46
3119	Quality Control	72	61	57	50
3122	Foreman	33	15	34	54
3323	Buyer	84	86	68	81
3341	Office Manager	76	91	58	78
3341	Team Leader	73	83	42	76
3511	IT Administrator	81	67	72	87
3512	Customer Support Worker	67	66	58	69
3538	Account Manager	53	93	48	67
4226	Receptionist	87	86	67	87
4232	Transport Clerk	70	69	57	65
4311	Accountant	74	51	73	79
4419	Assistant	73	70	71	68
4419	Office Worker	61	52	61	70
5120	Cook	26	10	27	12
5222	Sales Team Leader	37	36	28	46
5223	Retail assistant	25	15	29	15
5230	Cashier	36	11	10	15
5242	Financial advisor	10	59	18	10

Table 6.2 Share of vacancies that require English language skills across the Visegrad region. The occupations with the highest share are indicated in blue, the occupations with the lowest share in red

ISCO	Occupation	Czech Republic	Hungary	Poland	Slovakia
5242	Merchandiser	39	33	15	13
5242	Regional Sales Representative	48	27	35	68
5242	Sales Representative	41	36	29	38
5244	Telesales/Call Centre	29	16	23	50
7212	Welder	3	6	39	10
7231	Mechanic	20	10	32	16
7233	Locksmith	4	7	44	8
7411	Electrical Mechanic	44	3	26	32
7411	Electrician	23	6	42	16
8121	Labourer	5	8	12	5
8322	Driver	21	3	19	18
8344	Forklift Operator	9	5	7	4
9321	Packer/Auxiliary Labourer	4	14	11	11
9333	Warehouse Worker	11	7	10	13

Figure 6.1 Classification of occupations into three classes depending on the demand for English language skills across the Visegrad region

When repeating this analysis for German, it becomes clear that the results are noisier as there is much less variation across the occupations. For only 14 of the 236 country-occupation combinations, more vacancies were tagged ‘German’ than ‘English’. These are all artisan occupations, particularly welders and locksmiths, as well as nurses in the case of Slovakia. The latter result reflects the high level of circular migration of Slovak nurses to the German-speaking countries, in particular Austria (Bahna, 2014). In general, the demand for German does not seem so dependent on occupation complexity, as it is in the case of demand for English. We find several ‘manual’ occupations in the group with the highest demand for language skills (Figure 6.2).

Figure 6.2 Classification of occupations into three classes depending on the demand for German language skills across the Visegrad region

6.3 A wage premium for foreign language skills?

For two of the Visegrad countries, the Czech Republic and Slovakia, we were able to find data on the hourly wages (expressed in the national currency) for some occupations. The data are based on the median hourly gross wages, obtained from the WageIndicator web surveys collected from 2013 to Q1 2016. Our data cover 53 occupations for the Czech Republic and 49 occupations for Slovakia. While there is a clear positive correlation between the shares of vacancies that require English and wages in both (see Figure 6.3), the correlation between the German language demand and wages is much weaker and even negative for Slovakia (Figure 6.4). Following up on our previous line of thought that much of the demand for German speakers might be for jobs located in German-speaking countries, the lack of monetary premium associated with speaking German might be unobservable on the Slovak labour market simply because German speakers are collecting it abroad.

Figure 6.3 Correlation between the share of job advertisements that require English and the hourly wages in the Czech Republic and Slovakia

Source WageIndicator data for the Czech Republic and Slovakia

Figure 6.4 Correlation between the share of job advertisements that require German and the hourly wages in the Czech Republic and Slovakia

Source WageIndicator data for the Czech Republic and Slovakia

As a question about English proficiency was recently added to the WageIndicator survey, we can test its effect on the individual level as well. Table 6.3 shows by and large results we would intuitively expect: Experience and education increase earnings, along with living in the capital cities of Prague and Bratislava, holding a supervisory position and working in a high-skilled occupation and a partly of fully foreign-owned company. Experience squared, meanwhile, has a negative effect on earnings, along with female gender and being located in Slovakia as opposed to the Czech Republic. Effects of

firm size and private sector employment are insignificant. We find that English proficiency matters. Workers skilled in English earn more than those with no or only limited skills. Yet, basic proficiency in English does not seem to make a difference for wages, only workers who reach at least the ‘rather skilled’ level enjoy the earnings premium.

Table 6.3 OLS analysis of the impact of English proficiency on wages in the Czech Republic and Slovakia

		Coefficient	Standard error	
Individual characteristics	Years of Experience	0.024***	0.006	
	Years of Experience Squared	-0.000***	0.000	
	Years of Education	0.023***	0.008	
	Female	-0.229***	0.039	
	Living in the capital city (Prague or Bratislava)	0.238***	0.048	
	Living in Slovakia (compared to living in Czechia)	-0.097**	0.040	
	<i>English skill level (reference category: no English)</i>			
	- Basic	0.048	0.055	
- Rather skilled	0.186***	0.063		
- Skilled	0.193***	0.069		
Employer Characteristics	Private Company	-0.012	0.040	
	<i>Firm ownership (reference category: domestic owned company)</i>			
	- Partly foreign owned company	0.297***	0.090	
	- Fully foreign owned Company	0.137***	0.043	
	<i>Firm size (reference category: less than 20 workers)</i>			
- 20 to 50 workers	0.105	0.069		
- 50+ workers	0.092	0.059		
Occupation characteristics	ISCO 1-4 job	0.196***	0.039	
	Supervisory Position	0.113**	0.048	
	Constant	0.811***	0.143	
	Number of observations	437		
	R-squared	0.370		

* p<0.1; ** p<0.05; *** p<0.01

6.4 Summary

- One-third to three-fourths of the vacancies published on the four job boards demands foreign language skills (i.e. they carry a foreign language tag).
- English is the most-frequently-requested foreign language in the Visegrad group. 52% of the job advertisements calls for English language skills, yet less than one-third of the population is able to have a conversation in the language (according to the 2012 Eurobarometer). The demand for English is higher for occupations that are more complex than for those that are less complex. English thus is a language of professional and white collar workers. Moreover, English language skill comes with a wage premium.
- German, which is found in 12% of the job advertisements, is the second-most-in-demand foreign language in the Visegrad region. Interestingly, the 2012 Eurobarometer results reveal that 15% to 22% of the Visegrad population has sufficient German language skills to hold a conversation in the language. For German, there is no link between the demand for language skills and the complexity of an occupation.
- Other languages, such as French, Italian, Spanish and Russian, are only requested in a small minority of the vacancies. Only very few advertisements carry these tags.

7. Case Study 6: ‘Cross-cutting work on non-cognitive skills’

Throughout the case studies that are presented so far in this report, we looked into different types of skills, including cognitive skills. The last case study focuses on the *non-cognitive skills* (or ‘soft’ skills). As already stated earlier in this report, non-cognitive skills can be regarded as personality traits that, alongside cognitive skills, also impact social and economic outcomes such as educational attainment or earnings. Examples of non-cognitive skills are reliability, team-working skills and resistance to stress.

This final case study aims at providing an overview of what can be learnt from online vacancy data about the labour demand, i.e. employers’ requirements, in terms of non-cognitive skills. Unlike the other case studies in this report, which are all based on only one research paper, this case study is cross-cutting: it combines results on non-cognitive skills from three research works. Based on the ILO’s ISCO classification, the first two research works we present in this case study focus on low-skilled and medium-skilled occupations.⁵ The first paper analyses job advertisements posted on EURES, a public EU job portal, in Denmark, the Czech Republic and Ireland (Kureková *et al.*, 2015), whereas the second one explores vacancy data from Profesia.sk, the largest online job portal in Slovakia (Beblavý, *et al.*, 2016e). Finally, the last research work used in this case study is the work using vacancy data obtained from Burning Glass Technologies (Beblavý *et al.*, 2016c). This work was already presented in the second case study of this report (see Section 3.1.2), but here, we focus on the results on non-cognitive skills.

In the three works that we present in this case study, our approach uses very similar non-cognitive skills categorisations. They are based on our analysis of advertisements from EURES and Profesia.sk to identify skills that appear most frequently (these papers are not part of the InGRID project, but we discuss them here due to their high relevance). These categorisations divide non-cognitive skills into two different groups, *personal characteristics* and *social skills* (in Table 7.1). The former captures personal traits that determine how one approaches a task, including reliability, timeliness, independence, creativity, flexibility, manners and stress-resistance. The latter captures personal traits that determine how one interacts and communicates with others. This set of skills comprises communication, team-working and service skills.

In the remainder of this section, we first present the main results regarding non-cognitive skills of the three above-mentioned research works. Then we highlight the main differences and similarities across the five countries that are analysed (Denmark, Ireland, the Czech Republic, the United States and Slovakia).

⁵ Based on the ISCO classification, we consider occupations in category 9 (1st ISCO skill level) as low-skilled, and occupations in categories 4 to 8 (2nd skill level) as medium-skilled.

Table 7.1 **Categorisation of non-cognitive skills**

Social skills	Personal skills
Communication skills	Timeliness, punctuality
Service skills, customer approach	Independence
Team-working skills	Reliability
	Creativity
	Flexibility
	Resistance to stress
	Responsibility
	Pleasant demeanour and manners

Source Authors' own compilation. Note: responsibility and pleasant demeanour and manners are not mentioned in Kureková *et al.* (2015); timeliness/punctuality, creativity and resistance to stress are not mentioned in Beblavý, *et al.* (2016e); responsibility is not mentioned in Beblavý *et al.* (2016c)

7.1 'Employers' skill preferences across Europe: between cognitive and non-cognitive skills'

(Kureková *et al.*, 2015)

In this work, we seek to study the content of job advertisements for low- and medium-skilled occupations published on the public EU job portal EURES – the European Job Mobility Portal –, between March and July 2012. EURES, which was founded in 1993, is a platform that aims at providing information, advice and recruitment/placement services for workers and employers, as well as for any citizen wanting to take advantage of the free movement of persons. It is run by the European Commission (DG EMPL) and is free of charge for job seekers and employers. National public employment services (PES) link their own vacancy databases to the portal, where the openings are collected and posted in a semi-structured way and in pre-designed categories, creating a large 'standardised' collection of job openings across the participant countries. The portal is estimated to cover 30-40% of the overall European market for vacancies (Ackers, 2012). In 2012, on average 750,000 CVs were live in the system at any time in a given month, and about 26,000 employers had accounts.

We focus on three countries that are small open European economies: the Czech Republic, Denmark and Ireland. These countries are comparable in labour market size but differ in a number of aspects, e.g. economic structure, the design of education and skill formation systems, and the degree to which they have been affected by the recent economic crisis.

From the list of predefined occupational groups on the EURES website, we selected a range of medium- and low-skilled occupational groups from the service sector and industry. Medium-skilled occupations in the service sector include hotel, catering and sales staff (ISCO 5) and office staff (ISCO 4). Medium-skilled occupations in industry include metal and machinery workers (ISCO 7) and machine operators and assemblers (ISCO 8). Low-skilled service occupations include elementary occupations in sales, services, cleaning and various types of labourers in industry, all of which belong to ISCO 9. We downloaded the data by using self-developed custom-made software, which we dubbed 'grabber'. The grabber was programmed to download selected and identified fields from vacancies posted in a particular occupational group. A binary code for the job description field was then created to mark those advertisements where a particular skill or capability (from the list of skills in Table 7.1) was mentioned. We then proceeded with the analysis of data to calculate frequencies and simple statistics across occupations and across countries.

Table 7.2 shows how many job advertisements within a particular occupational group requested at least one skill or competence within one of the two groups of non-cognitive skills as defined earlier.⁶ The results reveal interesting variations among occupational groups within countries and also point to differences across the three countries analysed. In the Czech Republic, while non-cognitive skills, in particular social skills, are less sought in ‘industrial occupations’ (ISCO 7 and 8), they are also infrequently sought for the hotel and catering group, which is perhaps surprising. In Ireland, differences among occupational groups are less significant than in other countries. In the Danish labour market, employers seek non-cognitive personal characteristics (52.2% of vacancies request at least one particular skill in the non-cognitive personal skills group) more than experience (33.1% of job advertisements request experience), which is not the case in the Czech Republic and Ireland. Even for the non-cognitive social skills group, the share of job advertisements is relatively high in Denmark (31.5%), almost at the same level as experience (33.1%) and at a much higher level than formal degrees (13.5%). Conversely, in Ireland and the Czech Republic, the shares of vacancies referring to non-cognitive social skills and personal skills are lower than the shares of vacancies requesting experience (93.9% in Ireland, 60.7% in the Czech Republic) and formal degrees (22.0% in Ireland, 28.7% in the Czech Republic).

Table 7.2 Share of job advertisements requesting at least one particular non-cognitive skill, depending on the occupational groups (%)

		Hotel, catering and personal services staff	Sales staff and fashion work	Office staff	Metal, machinery and electronic equipment workers	Machine operators and assemblers	Sales, services and cleaning elementary occupations	Labourers in mining, construction manufacturing and transport	Total
Non-cognitive social	Czech Republic	5.2	23.6	27	2.4	3.1	7.2	3	9.2
	Ireland	10.8	-	15.0	6.3	-	10.6	3.5	10.7
	Denmark	22	48.2	52.7	26.1	25	25.5	13	31.5
Non-cognitive personal	Czech Republic	22.3	29.1	40.5	22	23.7	21.4	19.8	24.7
	Ireland	19.2	-	15.2	8.5	-	11.5	11.4	15.2
	Denmark	55.7	48.6	67.2	57.7	0	47.7	54.2	52.2

Source Kureková *et al.* (2015), based on EURES data

The results for each skill, competence or capability are presented separately in Table 7.3. In addition to skill frequencies (the share of job advertisements where a specific skill was explicitly demanded), we provide the sum of skills shares for each skill subcategory.

In the Czech labour market, non-cognitive social skills and personal characteristics are relatively more important for sales and fashion staff, and office staff. Communication skills, independence and reliability dominate. Non-cognitive skills are requested in addition to formal qualifications rather than instead of them, as in the Czech labour market formal qualifications remain important. In Ireland, some non-cognitive skills like communication and flexibility are more demanded than others on average. However, unlike in the Czech Republic, the variability among occupational groups is quite small. In particular, there is no clear-cut difference between service and industry sector occupations with respect to non-cognitive skills. Regarding the Danish labour market, non-cognitive skills are

⁶ In the Irish data, two occupational categories are missing, because we did not manage to obtain the target number of about 500 vacancies in each given cell.

highly requested, more than in the other two countries. Being service-oriented, having team skills, being independent and especially flexible are widely sought attributes. Among occupations, non-cognitive skills are more widely requested in service-related occupations.

Table 7.3 Share of job advertisements for which a particular skill was demanded (%)

			Hotel, catering and personal services staff	Sales staff and fashion work	Office staff	Metal, machinery and electronic equipment workers	Machine operators and assemblers	Sales, services and cleaning elementary occupations	Labourers in mining, construction manufacturing and transport	Total
Czech Republic	Non-cognitive social	Communication	4.8	23.3	25.5	1.9	1.8	6.6	2.2	8.5
		Service-oriented	0.2	1.3	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.6	0.0	0.3
		Team skills	0.3	0.5	2.8	0.9	1.8	1.3	0.9	1.0
		Total	5.3	25.0	28.6	2.8	3.5	8.5	3.0	9.8
	Non-cognitive personal	Timeliness	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.1
		Independence	10.1	11.4	21.1	13.7	10.1	6.3	5.2	11.6
		Reliability	9.5	13.0	17.1	9.5	12.7	12.1	12.4	11.4
		Creativity	1.6	1.3	1.0	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.9	0.9
		Flexibility	9.4	13.1	20.6	7.0	11.4	8.9	6.5	10.2
		Stress-resistant	1.0	0.7	4.7	0.4	0.9	1.3	0.2	1.1
Total	31.9	39.5	64.5	30.8	35.5	28.8	25.4	35.2		
Ireland	Non-cognitive social	Communication	4.8	-	13.0	4.5	-	8.1	0.0	6.8
		Service-oriented	1.2	-	0.7	0.0	-	0.4	0.9	0.8
		Team skills	5.3	-	2.9	2.2	-	2.9	2.6	3.8
		Total	11.3	-	16.7	6.7	-	11.5	3.5	11.5
	Non-cognitive personal	Timeliness	0.9	-	4.8	0.9	-	1.0	3.5	1.8
		Independence	0.1	-	0.0	0.4	-	0.2	0.0	0.1
		Reliability	5.7	-	1.4	3.1	-	1.9	5.3	3.7
		Creativity	1.9	-	0.5	0.0	-	0.0	0.0	0.9
		Flexibility	13.2	-	8.7	4.9	-	8.5	7.0	10.1
		Stress-resistant	1.4	-	1.2	0.9	-	0.6	0.0	1.1
Total	23.2	-	16.7	10.3	-	12.3	15.8	17.7		
Denmark	Non-cognitive social	Communication	1.7	1.6	9.9	1.8	0.0	2.2	0.5	2.9
		Service-oriented	9.4	42.1	36.0	11.6	0.0	19.4	1.6	22.0
		Team skills	13.1	21.3	27.4	14.4	25.0	5.6	11.5	15.1
		Total	24.2	65.0	73.4	27.8	25.0	27.2	13.5	40.0
	Non-cognitive personal	Timeliness	0.5	0.2	2.7	1.1	0.0	4.5	0.0	1.7
		Independence	20.0	19.3	36.0	34.2	0.0	22.1	27.1	24.5
		Reliability	7.4	8.2	3.0	12.0	0.0	6.6	27.1	8.6
		Creativity	12.1	10.9	2.7	1.8	0.0	1.3	0.5	5.9
		Flexibility	37.4	32.0	43.5	31.0	0.0	24.3	20.8	31.9
		Stress-resistant	4.5	6.3	16.4	3.5	0.0	2.2	1.0	5.6
Total	81.9	76.8	104.3	83.5	0.0	60.9	76.6	78.2		

Source Kureková *et al.* (2015), based on EURES data

7.2 'The surprisingly exclusive nature of medium- and low-skilled jobs - evidence from a Slovak job portal'

(Beblavý, et al., 2016e)

This work analyses the characteristics of labour demand by studying the content of job advertisements in Slovakia in selected low- and medium-skilled occupations. The data analysed in this work come from the largest online job portal in Slovakia (Profesia.sk). The company running the portal was established in 1997. The portal became a market leader in the early-to-mid 2000s and currently enjoys a market share of approximately 80% (Štefánik, 2012). It collects both vacancies and CVs.

We selected occupations with the aim of covering a wide range of low- and medium-skilled occupations from industry and services. Raw data were received from the portal database for the selected occupations for all advertisements posted between 2007 and 2011. After cleaning the data, we were left with over 50,000 distinct job advertisements to analyse. This selection of occupations covers 7.4% of all vacancies posted between 2007 and 2011. We used multiple techniques to process and code the data. In particular, the job description field in the advertisement was recoded to mark those vacancies in which a particular skill or capability from the categorisation of skills was mentioned, using a binary code.

Table 7.4 presents the shares of job advertisements requesting each skill, focusing on non-cognitive skills. Among the main results on non-cognitive skills of this work, we found that employers' skills demand for low- and medium-skilled jobs focuses on non-cognitive skills (and also specific cognitive skills) rather than on general cognitive skills. In the analysed vacancies, the most-requested requirement was previous experience (52%), followed by knowledge of languages (38%), responsibility (29%), communication skills (28%) and flexibility (24%). There seems to be a 'basic package' of non-cognitive skills (communication skills, flexibility and responsibility) that is required nearly across the board in Slovakia, together with specific cognitive skills like knowledge of foreign languages.

Another interesting finding is that skill intensity varies for occupations with the same level of education and is driven by demand for non-cognitive skills. For example, the education level required for engine driver and salesperson is similar, though these occupations differ markedly in their overall skill intensity. A much higher share of job advertisements for salesmen than for engine drivers requires non-cognitive skills. Non-cognitive skills are in particular related to interactive service occupations.

Table 7.4 Share of job advertisements requesting skills, depending on the occupation (%)

	Non-cognitive social				Non-cognitive personal					
	Communic	Team work	Pro-client	Average	Responsible	Reliable	Independent	Flexible	Demeanor	Average
Salesperson	59.0	9.3	9.8	26.0	31.5	16.9	25.6	32.7	32.3	27.8
Bartender	29.3	6.9	5.7	14.0	25.0	9.1	14.1	28.3	31.3	21.6
Waiter	28.2	7.3	5.1	13.5	27.1	9.4	14.4	26.2	29.9	21.4
Electrician	14.7	8.6	3.1	8.8	35.6	20.2	33.1	26.4	1.2	23.3
Courier	38.2	1.7	2.8	14.2	18.6	13.3	8.8	15.9	29.6	17.2
Au-pair	14.9	0.0	0.0	5.0	35.8	20.2	10.6	23.4	12.1	20.4
Romm staff	9.1	3.9	5.3	6.1	18.0	7.5	7.6	26.1	13.7	14.6
Cook	15.2	7.3	3.9	8.8	29.5	10.6	19.2	23.5	9.6	18.5
Driver	14.5	2.5	0.5	5.8	35.6	22.5	14.7	24.6	10.6	21.6
Forklift driver	3.9	8.9	0.3	4.4	40.1	21.5	19.8	24.1	0.3	21.2
Maintenance	10.6	7.1	0.1	5.9	27.6	9.2	27.3	18.8	1.3	16.8
Porter	22.5	1.3	0.7	8.2	27.2	21.2	6.0	19.2	21.2	18.9
Plumber	16.7	3.3	0.3	6.8	28.3	8.2	19.8	19.8	4.9	16.2
Bus driver	12.8	2.3	0.8	5.3	19.5	11.3	15.8	26.3	15.0	17.6
Cleaner	8.3	2.1	3.3	4.6	34.2	21.5	12.0	17.4	11.5	19.3
Truck driver	5.8	0.9	0.6	2.4	24.9	17.5	16.8	19.4	5.9	16.9
Caretaker	7.2	0.9	0.0	2.7	14.3	3.7	6.0	12.5	4.1	8.1
Assembly worker	8.4	9.0	1.4	6.3	25.7	13.1	19.3	15.1	2.4	15.1
Security guard	18.9	1.0	0.3	6.7	24.9	14.4	3.6	5.7	17.6	13.3
Tailor	12.9	14.6	1.0	9.5	30.9	6.1	20.9	5.6	3.5	13.4
Labourer	2.8	4.5	0.0	2.4	23.7	12.4	8.8	11.6	0.4	11.4
Engine driver	13.0	1.1	0.0	4.7	13.0	2.2	21.7	19.6	0.0	11.3
Postman	12.3	1.1	0.0	4.5	5.4	5.0	4.6	11.1	8.4	6.9
Total	28.4	6.7	4.6	13.2	28.8	14.3	18.3	23.9	17.9	20.6

Source Beblavý, *et al.* (2016e), based on profesia.sk data

7.3 'Skills Requirements for the 30 most-frequently advertised occupations in the United States'

(Beblavý *et al.*, 2016c)

*This work is based on vacancy data obtained from Burning Glass Technologies for the United States (Beblavý *et al.*, 2016c). It is already presented in the second case study of this report (in Section 3.1.2); so we only present results for non-cognitive skills here.*

With regards to the non-cognitive skills, we examined three sets of *social skills*, i.e. the service skills, communication skills and team-working skills, and 7 sets of *personal skills*, i.e. timeliness, independence, reliability, pleasant demeanor/manners, creativity, flexibility, and stress-resistant. Neither social nor personal skills appear to dominate one another. Both types of non-cognitive skills are frequently requested in vacancies. However, there are substantial differences between the sub-

categories within the groups of social and personal skills and across occupations. The range of values (i.e. the percentages of advertisements that contain the skills) is extensive.

Among the social skills, service skills are requested more than team-working and communication skills. Service skills (which also captures applicants' customer approach, client-orientation) appear in about 49% of the advertisements (and 45% if the average is calculated). This number varies between 7% and 91%. Variation across occupations is thus rather large. For 12 occupations, over half of the vacancies refer to service skills. For five occupations, no less than two-thirds of the vacancies mention service skills. These occupations are customer service representatives (66%), tellers (74%), retail salesperson (80%), sales agents, financial services (82%) and meeting, convention, event planners (91%). Given the nature of these occupations, which are all in the sales, services and support domains, it does not come as a surprise that they are at the top of the list in terms of percentages.

Communication skills are found in 23% of the vacancies. Across the 30 occupations, it is present in 3% to 63% of the vacancies. For four occupations, communication skills are listed in at least 30% of the vacancies: installation, maintenance, repair workers (31%), first-line office supervisors (32%), merchandise displayers (38%) and security guards (63%). Besides communication and service skills, team-working skills are also frequently mentioned in job advertisements: 31% of the vacancies refer to team work. For most of the 30 occupations, team work skills could be valuable. Of course, the role of the worker within the company and the firm's internal organisation can also have an impact on whether or not team work is needed. The percentage of vacancies that refers to team work ranges from 5% to 49%. 12 occupations show higher percentages than the average. The occupations with the highest percentages are supervisors of food preparation, serving workers (49%), general and operations managers (48%), combined food preparation workers (46%), retail salesperson (41%) and tellers (39%). For each of these occupations, one can imagine that team working skills are an important part of the position.

Table 7.5 Share of job advertisements across occupations with communication skills, service skills and team-working skills requirements

ISCO	Occupation	Share with communication skills (%)	Share with service skills (%)	Share with team-working skills (%)
1	General and Operations Managers	27	48	48
2	Computer Support Specialists	23	54	28
2	HR Specialists	24	34	30
3	Bookkeeping, Accounting, Auditing Clerks	21	34	25
3	First-Line Office Supervisors	32	57	34
3	Medical Assistants	19	27	26
3	Meeting, Convention, Event Planners	3	91	5
3	Nursing Assistant	18	12	25
4	Cashiers	27	58	23
4	CS Representatives	20	66	38
4	Medical Secretaries	22	29	21
4	Office Clerks	18	33	21
4	Secretaries	23	30	24
4	Tellers	30	74	39
5	Combined Food Preparation Workers	17	44	46
5	Cooks, Restaurant	19	21	29
5	Merchandise Displayers	38	46	31
5	Personal Care Aides	14	7	21
5	Retail Salesperson	22	80	41
5	Sale Worker Supervisors	28	61	37
5	Sales Agents, Financial Services	8	82	24
5	Sales Representative Wholesale	21	62	33
5	Security Guards	63	51	27
5	Supervisors Of Food Preparation, Serving Workers	22	43	49
7	Installation, Maintenance, Repair Workers	31	56	24
7	Maintenance Worker	18	19	22
8	Heavy Truck And Tractor Drivers	13	35	16
8	Light Truck, Delivery Service Drivers	20	43	19
9	Janitors and Cleaners	16	16	17
9	Labourers	12	26	23
	Across occupations	23	49	31

Source Beblavý *et al.* (2016c), based on Burning Glass data

We then zoom in on the personal non-cognitive skills. At first sight, the personal skills appear to be somewhat less related to specific jobs or occupations than the social skills. The percentages indeed vary from 3 to 33% across the 7 sets of skills (the averages range from 3 to 32%). More specifically, when considering all occupations, the percentage of job advertisements that lists timeliness and punctuality is 27% (ranging from 6 - 55%), independence 18% (2 - 44%), reliability 3% (0 - 13%), pleasant

demeanour, manners 15% (5-47%), creativity 24% (3-44%), flexibility 33% (15-60%) and stress-resistant 5% (0-35%). The highest correlations between the percentage of vacancies and the ISCO classification are found for timeliness (-0.45) and creativity (-0.48). As occupations become more complex, punctuality and creativity are required more often.

Table 7.6 below presents the five occupations with the highest share of vacancies that require a specific personal non-cognitive skill. When the share was the same for multiple occupations, all these occupations are reported. Interestingly, there are a number of occupations that are in the top 5 for several of the skills: security guards, general and operations managers, meeting, convention, event planners, first-line office supervisors and tellers are present for at least three of the skills.

Table 7.6 The five occupations with the highest share of vacancies that require each of the 7 skills listed (when more than five occupations are listed – there were multiple occupations with the same percentages, 1 = highest percentage, 5 = lowest)

	Timeliness	Independence	Reliability	Demeanour	Creativity	Flexibility	Stress-resistant
1	Meeting, Convention, Event Planners	Security Guards	Tellers	Security Guards	Sale Worker Supervisors	Merchandise Displayers	Security Guards
2	Security Guards	Merchandise Displayers	Personal Care Aides	Cashiers	Tellers	Sales Agents, Financial Services	Medical Secretaries
3	General and Operations Managers	HR Specialists, Secretaries	Bookkeeping, Accounting, Auditing Clerks	Meeting, Convention, Event Planners	Computer Support Specialists	Meeting, Convention, Event Planners	First-Line Office Supervisors
4	First-Line Office Supervisors		First-Line Office Supervisors, CS Representatives, Office Clerks, Secretaries	Merchandise Displayers	CS Representatives, General and Operations Managers	Sale Worker Supervisors	Personal Care Aides, Medical Assistants
5	Sales Representatives Wholesale	General and Operations Managers		Medical Secretaries		Tellers	

Source Beblavý *et al.* (2016c), based on Burning Glass data

7.4 What are the main similarities and the main differences among the five countries analysed in this case-study?

Regarding low-skilled and medium-skilled occupations, the first important difference among the five countries analysed in this case-study is the separation between a group of ‘more formalised’ labour markets (Czech Republic, Ireland and US) and a group of ‘less formalised labour market’ (Denmark and Slovakia). In this study, we use this term to indicate that cognitive skills are more demanded than non-cognitive skills. In other words, the former group comprises countries where cognitive skills are more demanded than non-cognitive ones, whereas the latter comprises countries where non-cognitive skills are more demanded.

In the group of ‘more formalised’ labour market, the Czech Republic is the first example. In the Czech Republic, formal education is requested widely with the exception of selected service occupations. More than non-cognitive skills, cognitive abilities prevail and this is the case also in the service-related occupations. In the least skilled segment, reliability and flexibility are sought. Regarding the dominance of cognitive skills, there are similarities between the Czech Republic and Ireland, where experience and a range of cognitive skills (including knowledge of English) prevail over non-cognitive skills and characteristics. The US can also be included in this group of ‘more formalised’ labour markets, as the role of non-cognitive social skills and personal traits seem to be relatively small in the skills required for low- and mid-skilled occupations.

Conversely, employers in the Danish labour market demand much less formal education and cognitive abilities, and from this perspective labour demand is less formalised. In Denmark, it is strongly focused on non-cognitive skills and abilities across occupational types, with flexibility, good customer skills and team skills considered as asset. Similarly, in Slovakia, low- and medium-skilled jobs advertisements focuses on non-cognitive skills and specific cognitive skills rather than on general cognitive skills (e.g. the ability to learn).

Another important finding, when we compare the results for the five countries, is the confirmation of the hypothesis that the specific skill set demanded in service occupations differs from other, mainly industrial-sector (manual) jobs: there is greater focus on non-cognitive social skills and personal characteristics. At the same time, there is great variation in the content of skill demand across the labour markets analysed, and while on average non-cognitive skills might be more desired in interactive service jobs, these requirements might appear in addition to formal education, not instead of it.

Finally, we also find interesting differences among countries when it comes to the specific non-cognitive skills that are required. One example is the hierarchy among the three specific social skills (communication, service skills, and team-working skills). In the US and Denmark, service skills are requested more than team-work and communication skills. Conversely, in Slovakia, Ireland and the Czech Republic, communication seems to be the most important of the three specific social skills.

7.5 Summary

- Non-cognitive skills have received much attention in recent years, as there is a growing number of academic and policy contributions that highlights their importance in the labour market.
- Our work focuses on the prevalence of non-cognitive skills in vacancies and is comparative in nature. More specifically, we examined the Czech Republic, Denmark, Ireland, Slovakia and the United States.
- In four of the countries studied, cognitive skills are more often requested than non-cognitive skills. In the other two countries, the opposite holds.
- Demand for non-cognitive skills is widespread, even for low- and medium-skilled occupations. Moreover, non-cognitive skills are particularly important in the service sector (and the emphasis there seems to be on social skills rather than personal non-cognitive skills).

8. Conclusions

This paper presented the findings of six case studies, each based on web data, to assess the potential of using vacancies and meta data extracted from online job boards to study occupations and skills. We show how such data can be used to analyse different types of *occupations*, of all skill levels, and *skills*, such as education, experience, cognitive and non-cognitive skills. Our case studies covered several different countries and topics, e.g. mismatches in the educational requirements listed in job vacancies and the educational attainments of job holders in the Czech Republic, requirements of US employers for the 30 most-frequently-advertised occupations, foreign languages skills in the Visegrad region and a new way to identify new and emerging occupations in Europe. Our study is a successful proof-of-concept and contributes to a rapidly expanding research field.

appendix 1

a1.1 List of the 30 most-frequently-advertised occupations in the US

Table a1.1 below presents the 30 most-frequently-advertised occupations in the United States (as obtained from Burning Glass Technologies). For each occupation, it shows the ISCO code and the number of job advertisements available in the dataset. On average, there are 66,292 vacancies for each occupation. There are no occupations for which fewer than 30,000 job advertisements are available. For five occupations, there are over 100,000 vacancies in the database. These occupations are: retail salesperson (233,851 vacancies), CS (i.e. customer service) representative (197,232 vacancies), sale worker supervisor (164,298 vacancies), secretary (114,918 vacancies) and sales representative wholesale (111,177 vacancies).

The ISCO code of each occupation is reported in the first column of Table a1.1 (the ISCO-08 code). The *ISCO-08 classification* is the most recent version of the International Labour Organisation's (ILO) '*International Standard Classification of Occupations*', which was first launched in the 1980s. In ISCO-08, occupations are categorised into 9 classes on the basis of the skill level and the skill specialisation needed to perform the tasks that they involve. Occupations with complex tasks have a lower ISCO code (e.g. 'managers' are grouped under ISCO code 1), whereas occupations with less complex tasks have a higher ISCO code (e.g. 'elementary occupations' are grouped under ISCO code 9). The 9 ISCO-08 groups are: 1 '*Managers*', 2 '*Professionals*', 3 '*Technicians and associate professionals*', 4 '*Clerical support workers*', 5 '*Service and sales workers*', 6 '*Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers*', 7 '*Craft and related trades workers*', 8 '*Plant and machine operators, and assemblers*', and 9 '*Elementary occupations*' (not considering 0 Armed forces occupations).

Table a1.1 Overview of the 30 most-frequently-advertised occupations in the US, their ISCO codes and the number of vacancies collected

ISCO	Occupation	Number of vacancies
1	General and Operations Managers	30,641
2	Computer Support Specialists	37,705
2	HR Specialists	36,243
3	Bookkeeping, Accounting, Auditing Clerks	43,445
3	First-Line Office Supervisors	35,841
3	Medical Assistants	40,127
3	Meeting, Convention, Event Planners	32,204
3	Nursing Assistant	96,937
4	Cashiers	29,722
4	CS Representatives	197,232
4	Medical Secretaries	35,263
4	Office Clerks	42,948
4	Secretaries	114,918
4	Tellers	68,339
5	Combined Food Preparation Workers	46,912
5	Cooks, Restaurant	30,252
5	Merchandise Displayers	60,100
5	Personal Care Aides	38,106
5	Retail Salesperson	233,851
5	Sale Worker Supervisors	164,298
5	Sales Agents, Financial Services	36,172
5	Sales Representative Wholesale	111,177
5	Security Guards	66,122
5	Supervisors of Food Preparation, Serving Workers	45,957
7	Installation, Maintenance, Repair Workers	43,157
7	Maintenance Worker	94,066
8	Heavy Truck and Tractor Drivers	33,180
8	Light Truck, Delivery Service Drivers	38,405
9	Janitors and Cleaners	33,779
9	Labourers	71,669

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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